

Assessing the Effectiveness of Combined Technical Indicators for Predicting Bitcoin Market Direction

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19th January 2025

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

It is my pleasure to acknowledge my heartfelt gratitude to all the people who have supported and assisted me in the completion of this research.

Firstly, I would like to thank Dr. Dilina Herath (PhD), Academic Dean, School of Business, ESOFM Metro Campus for giving me valuable assistance and making this research academically sound.

I would like to extend my deepest gratitude to my supervisor Dr. S. D. Jayasooriya (PhD), Senior Lecturer of General Sir John Kotelawala Defense University for his support, constructive criticism and constant encouragement during this research process.

I would also like to make an acknowledgment to Mr. Damith Pathirana, the Centre Manager of ESOFM Metro Campus – Matara, for providing me with the essential resources and administrative assistance which were immensely helpful in the successful completion of this study.

Last, the participants in this study deserve my gratitude for their time and honest answers that formed the foundation of the findings in this study.

Keywords: Bitcoin; technical indicators; market prediction; RSI; MACD; cryptocurrency trading; algorithmic trading

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This research focuses on the combined technical indicators of Relative Strength Index (RSI), Moving Average Convergence Divergence (MACD), Bollinger Bands, Exponential Moving Average (EMA), and Moving Averages as predictors of Bitcoin market direction. Following quantitative/qualitative research design, self-completed questionnaires and interviews were employed for the evaluation of decision-making standards, prediction efficiency, volatility influence, and timeframe sensitivity.

The outcomes demonstrated the idea of having the combined of the different indicators enhances the efficacy and the level of the prediction in the medium- and long-term timeframes. It was found that combined indicators were more robust in volatile markets, though there were challenges when the two forms of volatility, namely idiosyncratic and systematic, were present. RSI proved to be an exception and demonstrated good results on all timeframes.

The above conclusions illustrate the importance of the combined indicator approaches and the importance of the specificity of the goal and task of trading. Specific recommendations are provided for the traders and the researchers with references to the volumes and macroeconomic environment for further development of the prediction models and possible future studies. The rationality of this work substantially helps develop the understanding of applying technical indicators in Bitcoin market analysis.

CHAPTER ONE: INTRODUCTION

Due to the high growth and volatility of the cryptocurrency market, Bitcoin has become one of the most attractive and well-known trading opportunities. While conventional trading techniques do not fit the newer features of trading in cryptocurrencies, the use of technical indicators to increase the accuracy of the trading decisions process has become popular.

“Technical indicators are heuristic or pattern-based signals produced by the price, volume, and/or open interest of a security or contract used by traders who follow technical analysis” (investopedia.com). Technical indicators involving historical price and volume characteristics of Bitcoin can be used to predict the potential market’s direction, velocity, and possible turnarounds. This research evaluates the use of multiple technical indicators to determine the most accurate future market condition in Bitcoin.

It expands the significance of using technical indicators within the cryptocurrency market as traders have progressed towards using several indicators to improve the accuracy of the forecast. Well-known indicators, like MA, RSI, or Bollinger Bands and Fibonacci retracement, have been presumably used to define trends, momentum, and reversals. Overall, each of these indicators has its role –Moving Averages work to filter out the price data to give clearer picture about the market Moving averages – The RSI on the other hand helps traders to identify indicators of over sold or over bought signals that may indicate an impending market adjustment. While Bollinger Bands, in contrast, show a volatility zone or price volatility and potential breakout areas.

In addition, using combinations of these indicators, it becomes easier to eliminate noise information and minimize false signals that can lead to poor decision making. For instance, the importance of signals from the RSI indicator and Bollinger Bands may be stronger in reversal compared to reliance on either one alone. This multi-layered approach is beneficial in reducing risks involved in a very volatile market such as Bitcoin.

1.1 Background of the Study

The cryptocurrency market, especially Bitcoin, has grown rapidly from the very beginning of its launch and has become an influential part of the financial industries. It has a high level of volatility and gives traders 24/7 trading opportunity, which differentiates it from other financial markets.

With Bitcoin being dominant in the cryptocurrency market, traders tend to find the right ways for embracing this market to capitalize on price fluctuations. Among the most popular adopted analysis techniques is the application of technical indicators, these are statistical measures based on historical price and volume data. They help trend-following traders to see where the market is heading, when it is moving at full speed or when the direction may be changing.

Technical indicators, such as Moving Averages, Relative Strength Index (RSI), and Bollinger Bands, are widely used by traders to obtain trade entries. Traditionally, these indicators have been employed singularly to help trade in Bitcoin. But due to the highly volatile and

constantly changing conditions in the Bitcoin market, a respective single key indicator might be insufficient. This limitation has created an interest in exploring using multiple technical indicators to increase the accuracy of trade decisions.

Although trading with technical indicators is popular, the literature concerning the effectiveness of their combination, particularly for Bitcoin, is limited. It still seems that most of the previous research were concerned with the results of the single indicator only, without considering the combined influence (e.g., *Effectiveness of the Relative Strength Index Signals in Timing the Cryptocurrency Market* by Marek Zatwarnicki, Krzysztof Zatwarnicki and Piotr Stolarski). This limitation pointed out the importance of examining the effectiveness of different technical indicators in together to improve trading outcomes.

It is needed to investigate how these technical indicators perform in combination to formulate efficient trading strategies which take into account the fluctuating and variable nature of the Bitcoin market. This research has been done to fill this gap by conducting an analysis of the effectiveness of various technical indicators in relation to trading in Bitcoin. In doing so, it aimed to extend prior knowledge regarding the best way in which these indicators can be used to optimize trading performance.

Additionally, there also emerged new tendencies towards the use of several technical indicators simultaneously as well as new features of the Bitcoin market that the traditional financial market did not have. Regarded for its peer-to-peer payment system, no supervision from authorities (Decentralization), and its 24/7 trading hours, made Bitcoin a financial product in which price fluctuations were mainly driven by factors from outside the traditional financial markets and macroeconomic occurrences. These reasons drove traders to try more complex approaches when using technical indicators to arrive at the right decision since one indicator could not adequately address the direction of such a dynamic market.

The volatility of BITCOIN price meant that it was possible to only rely on the leading indicators or the lagging indicators. Both had to be used in this case. Some of the indicators like RSI or even Fibonacci retracement traded before reversals happened while other indicators such as the Moving Average traded once a trend has been established. With that choice of tools traders would have a much better ability to pivot into new trends or out of consolidation phases that frequently occur in Bitcoin trading.

The presence of Institutional Investors is largely the major driving force behind the market behaviors of Bitcoin. In the process, institutional demand had emerged wherein big investors started investing in Bitcoin through funds, ETFs, and straight purchases. This unprecedented inflow not only introduced fresh dynamism to the liquidity, price level stability and the sentiment in the market. Such fundamental measurements, which once at one point yielded accurate results due to the prevalent retail-broker age market, did not sufficiently capture this new institutional influx. Therefore, it is possible to trace how some combination of the different indicators enabled traders to adapt to new structures of the market.

One more factor influencing trading in Bitcoin is the so-called market sentiment and its impact on technical trading. Often, wild fluctuations in price of Bitcoin not always explained by the supply and demand law but by the behavior of traders, their emotions. These cycles of fear and greed were more pronounced in the crypto market owing to the fact that the market is mainly speculative and largely driven by news regarding this market which can easily go viral on social media. Indicators like the RSI show the level of momentum, and the level of overbought/oversold situations rises in the determination of reversal patterns, that is, market

movements caused by emotional influences. In addition to such indicators as Volume indicator, traders received wider information on how fluctuations in sentiment influenced prices.

Furthermore, significant changes in the way of applying the technical indicators took place because of the algorithmic trading advent in the cryptocurrency territory. Those algorithms, which were programmed to perform trades in response to certain parameters and technical signals, were extremely fast at processing information and were performing their trades within milliseconds. Therefore, the ability of these technical indicators to produce trade signals which were required for technical analysis in this new kind of institutional automated trading environment had to be reassessed. This trend brought new chances for the traders to create a plan of action that implied more than one sign to enhance chances of a successful trade in a rapidly growing automated world.

Finally, this research aimed at looking at an effort of blending the technical indicators in order to determine accurate trade entries which not only enhance accurate trades but also to come up with a framework that would capture the real nature of the Bitcoin market. The insights publicized in the work were meant to add to the limited body of knowledge regarding technical analysis of cryptocurrency trading so as to inform improved patterns of trading. The study found out that there's needed to adopt flexibility in the formulation of strategies especially when dealing with markets such as the volatile Bitcoins market. Such knowledge of interaction between various technical aids and market situations could help the traders align themselves to wait for the right technique that could unveil the opportunities while avoiding detrimental pitfalls.

1.2 The Problem Statement & Justification

The problem statement of this research was “to assess the effectiveness of combined technical indicators for predicting Bitcoin market direction, addressing the gap in existing literature on how multiple technical indicators can be integrated into single trading strategy by enhancing the prediction accuracy in a highly volatile and unpredictable market.”

Cryptocurrencies, especially the Bitcoin market, is highly volatile, thus determining the exact direction that will prevail in the market is very complicated. The stock markets have for a long time been using technical indicators for analyzing the market and conducting trades. But their applicability in the cryptocurrency market is relatively unknown, particularly when they are used simultaneously.

Unlike the traditional markets, Bitcoin has somewhat lower influence from outside variables such as global politics, currency exchange rates and economical inflation. This enables that the Bitcoin having a better response in technical analysis making it an ideal instrument for researching the effectiveness of technical indicators. The application of specific technical indicators like Moving Averages (MA), Relative Strength Index (RSI) and Moving Average Convergence Divergence (MACD) has been researched in different financial literature but their application and significance on forecasting the market direction of Bitcoin did not been given much consideration (e.g., *Autoregressive Integrated Moving Average Model based Prediction of Bitcoin Close Price by Anupriya; Shruti Garg – 2018, Predicting bitcoin returns*

using high-dimensional technical indicators by Jing-Zhi Huang; William Huang; Jun Ni - 2019).

The lack of proper predictive methods can lead to irrational market choices, revenue losses for brokers and traders, and ultimately, economical losses for investors. This also leads to market anomalies that may have prices skewed with true value since trading is subject to sudden decisions informed by ambiguous signals. Furthermore, the Bitcoin market appears volatile and uncertain for institutional investors, which could prevent cryptocurrencies from gaining mass appeal as an asset class.

This means that if this problem is not addressed it will take time for people to come to terms with the fact that it's hard to predict Bitcoins market direction hence resulting in more complexities, vulnerabilities, and even disorientation mostly including loss of money through trading bitcoins. Market manipulation by those who are seeking to reap short-term gains instead of investing in the actual value of the asset cannot be ruled out, and as a result, the market could still remain more of a gambling ground than an efficient market where value is created. In addition, weak predictive tools may hinder the progress of technical algorithms involving a forecast of market pattern and trends essential in the fabrication of automatic trading systems, which may ultimately hinder the advancement of technological innovation of cryptocurrency markets.

Whenever measuring the efficiency of synchronized technical indicators, proper attention was to be paid to the innovational tendencies influencing cryptocurrency trading, with the emphasis on data-based technologies. This reduced the amount of centralized control and ushered in changes such as real-time analytics and block chain data collection to the way traders considered Bitcoin. For the first time, blockchain data that helped to analyze volumes of transactions, miners and wallets were integrated with traditional technical analysis tools. This addition provided traders with further effective tools and additional fundamental blockchain indexes that they can use in their trading.

However, the entrance of decentralized finance (DeFi) and its effects on Bitcoins trading also was another factor to address. Bitcoin trading, lending and borrowing, which in some of the decentralized finance (DeFi) protocols were made possible, impacted the liquidity and price swings of Bitcoin. There was a need for new technical indexes that considered the higher activity in decentralized platforms, through which the price might be influenced by such factors as variations in the liquidity of an asset, or some update in the protocol. Such change in market conditions, therefore, called for a shift in the process of integrating different indicators, including price-analogue signals, and new signals associated with the block chain.

Moreover, fluctuations in the price of Bitcoin began to depend on the psychological effects of social media. Some online applications which include X (previously known as Twitter) and Reddit have influenced traders' sentiments that cause short-term volatility including boosting or crashing of stock value. The use of social media feeds was brought into traders' technical analysis arriving with tools that analyzed the sentiment of the data. This development meant that the market began to gravitate toward integrating regular technology signs with genuine sentiment information to strengthen prediction precision in less stable conditions where news and rumors drastically influenced the price trends.

1.3 Research Objectives

General objective: To assess the effectiveness of combined technical indicators for predicting Bitcoin market direction.

Specific objectives:

- To find the relationship between the effectiveness of combined technical indicators and the prediction of Bitcoin market direction.
- To identify the optimal technical indicator combination for a specific timeframe to predict the Bitcoin market direction.

1.4 Significance of the Study

This research had important theoretical implications as it brought the understanding of technical analysis in the field of finance and, more specifically, in the context of cryptocurrencies. While this had been researched previously in traditional asset classes, particularly stocks and forex, the characteristics of Bitcoin and other cryptocurrencies are different from them in a number of ways. This made the re-evaluation of the same tools essential. Conducting research on the efficiency of combined technical analysis tools to determine the direction of Bitcoin's market movements contributed to expanding current theoretical approaches concerning the cryptocurrency market. This research can also open avenues for further research in other similar digital assets which expand the theoretical knowledge base of modern financial markets.

On an empirical level, this research supplied a factual and comparative analysis of the results got with actual information, which indicated the effectiveness of combined technical indicators when applied for the analysis of Bitcoin price fluctuations. Thus, the study employed powerful statistical techniques and back-testing approaches and generated empirical results that can support or refute the existing assumptions about the dynamics within the crypto markets. These results proved useful for refining future predictive models and can be a foundation for other researchers and financial analysts.

Benefited Parties:

1. **Traders and Investors:** The direct target consumers of this research was the trading community comprising of both small independent traders, institutional traders and investors in the drive for cryptocurrencies. The information derived from this work could assist them in improving the ways they approach trades and mitigate risk and possibly improving returns due to a better and more knowledgeable approach.

For traders and investors, the findings of this research provided a more precise tool in risk management while also providing new knowledge about trading strategies. With a systemic approach to analyzing combined technical indicators, these people would significantly decrease the anxious pitfalls which are inherent in tense trading situations. This was due to the increased predictive power of that approach so that traders could rely less on their instincts and more by their algorithms in such inherently volatile asset class as Bitcoin.

Moreover, for institutional investors, who trade with larger number of bitcoins and utilized more extended duration of time and often had different strategies, the identification of combined indicators allowed refusing misinformation by sorting out periodical fluctuations and volatility of Bitcoin. Due to this they were better placed to manage risks and make appropriate decisions concerning portfolios diversification and cryptocurrency investments. Finally, through enhancing the trader and investor with sophisticated tools and methods, this research tried to increase the stability of the market and to help the participants take the right action and make the right decision in the right time.

2. **Financial Analysts and Portfolio Managers:** The implications of this study will also be useful to professionals that are involved in the preparation of financial analysis and portfolio management. They can, in turn, use these findings to recommend the right combination of technical indicators to clients and adjust the portfolio's investments in the Bitcoin market, which commonly is viewed as being highly risky and uncertain.

To financial analysts and portfolio managers, this research offered real-life tools to examine and integrate cryptocurrency investments into a range of investment portfolios. Such professionals could provide more accurate advice to clients on how to deal with Bitcoin by analyzing the efficiency of the combination of the indicators in question. Enabling analysts to identify better entry and exit of Bitcoin such talents were instrumental in optimizing the execution of assets recommendation.

Moreover, this study described methods for hedging Bitcoin positions by using more accurate measures to manage risks related to changing portfolio weights and return forecasts for managers with multiple assets to manage. With the help of these strange results, analysts and managers could thus adjust their tactics to avoid such risks and get higher profitability investments, making Bitcoin a more valid option in client portfolios relying on conventional less unpredictable assets. This research did, therefore, enable the construction of the views on cryptocurrency investments in a manner that would be consistent with both the risk tolerance as well as the investment goals of the financial professional.

3. **Financial Technology (FinTech) Firms:** The empirical evidence this research will offer benefit companies that are involved in the development of algorithm trading platforms, trading bots, and other integrated financial technologies. An analysis of such indicators can help outline the best combinations that can be used in more complex trading algorithms that may form the basis of the enhanced trading platforms suitable for cryptocurrency markets.

Additionally, these insights were instrumental to advanced analytics in trading platforms of FinTech firms as they presented their clients with a better option for formulating decisions than traditional models. For firms developing software for institutional and retail traders, this study highlighted the need for accurate indicator portfolio to capture fast moving markets where traders could find clients seeking competitive advantage in cryptocurrency trading. Finally, the results of this study allowed FinTech firms to refine their understanding of the Information Systems with

the creation of advanced, consumer-oriented solutions for meeting brand new demands within the financial markets for cryptocurrencies.

4. **Academia and Future Researchers:** This research will also be useful to the academic audience who studies financial markets, technical analysis and cryptocurrencies. The results of the study will be useful for the further development of the existing academic debate regarding the relevance of the existing theoretical finance in the new markets by providing a base for it.

To academia and future researchers, this study provided an insight into technical analysis within the dynamic environment of cryptocurrencies. Analyzing the efficiency of combined indicators, the studies were given the empirical base by which it becomes possible to challenge and develop the traditional theories of the financial markets which was mostly devoted to such effective stock and forex as the assets categories. On this basis, scholars were able to examine whether classical models of finance could be employed to describe highly unpredictable and decentralized markets, like Bitcoin.

In addition, this research has opened doors for further research by providing a framework of reference where subsequent researchers could commence with when studying other digital aid and new markets. Approving combined indicators for Bitcoin, the study suggested that the following research can investigate other altcoins or even wider use in decentralized finance (DeFi) sphere. Thus, the research undertaken played the role of a starting point for the formation and the improvement of the essentially diverse financial theories for the contemporary markets which in its turn expanded the theories underlying the education and research of the finance discipline.

1.5 Scope of the Study

This study sought to investigate the efficiency of a specific set of technical indicators in determining the direction of the Bitcoin market. This was done with the help of historical prices data and feedback from traders who use technical indicators for Bitcoin trading. These indicators tested for their efficacy in various market conditions by the study. Bull and bear market phases are used to sensitize the analysis.

The above scope of this study also involved the careful selection of specific technical indicators that are more universally known and applied to the Bitcoin trading market among other markets, such as Moving Averages, Relative Strength Index (RSI), and Moving Average Convergence Divergence (MACD). These indicators were chosen for use because they are popular among traders and because their theory involves predicting the direction of the market. As such, the research was designed to focus on a certain combination of indicators in order to avoid overwhelming data that would not necessarily help to identify clear, tangible areas for improvement.

Moreover, it was desirable to specify several combinations of these indicators in an effort to investigate if they yielded better predictive abilities in combination compared with individual analysis. This approach allowed for the consideration of the problem of using single

indicators in the highly fluctuating market such as Bitcoin, in which various market conditions may require a more comprehensive set of signals. Therefore, the scope allowed implementation of various sets, which in turn helped to define which two or several indicators, acting together, were more effective in different trading conditions.

The fact that trader feedback transitioned to becoming a primary type of data dictated the study's specificity in terms of practical relevance. To ensure the study captured the true performance of these indicators, the work included direct opinions from traders who actively engaged in the use of these indicators when participating in the Bitcoin markets. This qualitative dimension attempted at reconciling a number of empirical discoveries contained in historical price data or at refuting them on the basis of subsequent theoretical a priori analysis. It provided, therefore, a means of moving from formalistic concepts to their actual operationalization.

1.6 Limitations of this study

The study concerned only Bitcoin as it is the most popular cryptocurrency. However, it did not include a comparison with other cryptocurrencies. Even though during the study a number of typically popular technical indicators chose, it did not encompass all the indicators. Focusing on a limited number of indicators helped to conduct focused research. Also, the study did not incorporate any factors rooted in macroeconomic, political or geopolitical within its framework. More specifically, the research did rely on technical approaches strictly. This way the boundaries could be clearly outlined and by doing so, the study was set to provide different insights that are actionable all while recognizing that there are more fields that can be explored.

Limitations of this study:

- The study did not consider macroeconomic, political, or geopolitical factors.
- The study did not account for trader sentiment or behavioral factors.
- Findings were specific to Bitcoin and could not be generalizable to other cryptocurrencies or financial markets.
- Based on historical daily price data, limited timeframe considered for analysis.

1.7 Chapter Profiles

Chapter 1: Introduction

Chapter One of this research provided the context of the study by outlining the market characteristics of Bitcoin as well as the technical analysis approach that traders can apply in the market. The study also pointed out the lack of research on the simultaneous utilization of these indicators for Bitcoin, stated the main goals and objectives of the study, and explained its importance for traders, analysts, and developers. It also described the study's limitations wherein the technical factors were solely considered in the study.

Chapter 2: Literature Review

This chapter aims to offer a synthesis of existing literature concerning technical analysis in cryptocurrencies. It started with the industry analysis consisting of Bitcoin market position, its competitors, and the current state of trading. Specific concepts related to the study were defined first before discussing theoretical frameworks and previous research on technical analysis. The lack of prior studies dealing with the combined usage of the indicator for trading Bitcoins led to the formulation of research questions, framework, and hypotheses for the study, providing a robust context for the analysis.

Chapter 3: Research Methodology

This chapter focused on the method of the study and highlighted the research paradigm and the methods of participant selection. It explained how data was collected, focusing on how feedback from the trader and historical Bitcoin data was obtained. To strengthen data analysis, analytical tools and statistical testing techniques were adopted as the data analysis approach. It also discussed steps that were taken to ensure data credibility and issues to do with the use of ethics in the research work.

Chapter 4: Data Presentation and Analysis

The data collected from traders and the analysis of historical data were shown and discussed in this chapter. Data reliability was first checked and then description of participants' characteristics was conducted. In order to look at the associations between various variables, hypothesis was posed, and regression analysis was conducted to understand predictive trends. A discussion connected these outcomes to the purpose of this research, providing interpretations in view of past studies.

Chapter 5: Conclusion and Recommendations

The last chapter highlighted the study conclusions and provided guidance for traders on how to apply the discovered knowledge. Several short-term and long-term steps that could be taken to enhance the use of bitcoins in trading were proposed. The chapter also suggested more probable directions of research, investigating other cryptocurrencies and markets in terms of combined technical indicators.

CHAPTER TWO: LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 INTRODUCTION

In the process of conducting this literature review, the process of the technical indicators' development and its application in the field of the financial markets was described in general while taking into consideration Bitcoin and cryptocurrencies markets. To conceptualize the ways in which technical indicators have been adopted in the past, this chapter outlined how technical analysis has progressed in conventional markets as well as how technical indicators have been used within evolving cryptocurrency markets. As specific areas of discussion the following points have been identified. The analysis of the concept of combined indicators the effectiveness and shortcomings of the use of the combined indicators and directions of further development of the topic that was discussed.

This chapter also discussed the fact that due to specific features of the cryptocurrency market such as real-time 24/7 market, decentralized market, and high sensitivity to price changes. Traditional technical analysis tools needed to be reconsidered due to these variations of the cryptocurrency market. By analyzing previous literature, the present chapter delineated the advantages and drawbacks of use of common technical indicators in the Bitcoin market. Particular emphasis was placed on consideration of the existence of limitations connected with the use of a single technical indicator, which in turn led to the concept of combined indicators that this research tested to enhance the forecast accuracy.

Also, this chapter explained the theoretical advancement in the area of market analysis. Several conceptual frameworks were pursued to ground the knowledge, wherein multiple technical indicators are integrated in an effort to present novel perspectives on trading in cryptocurrencies. This chapter also discussed that the industry has shifted the competition and trends indicating that the newest fintech tools have appeared and traders depend on these tools in the process of analysis. On this basis, this review succeeded in justifying the significance and imperative of the present research to the development of new theory and practical applications for the analysis of the cryptocurrency market.

2.2 Industrial Overview

2.2.1 Background of the Industry

The Bitcoin market remains prominent as a keystone of the cryptocurrency market with more than 45% of total cryptocurrency market capitalization as of 2023 (*CoinMarketCap.com, 2023*). Bitcoin's main use as electronic money, while being a decentralized digital asset, has put it in a different category from rivals such as Ethereum and Litecoin, which operate in other sections of the decentralized blockchain environment. For example, in smart contracts or in the provision of faster transactions, respectively (*Buterin, 2021*). These trade-offs make Bitcoin unique due to its scarcity, complete decentralization and increasing recognition as the 'digital gold'. This is why Bitcoin is the preferred asset in company portfolios by investors who want to diversify away from the inflating financial markets (*Nakamoto, 2008*). As competitors press on with the development and the diversification of the application of this blockchain technology, Bitcoin has maintained its position as the pioneer, reaping the benefit of the branding factor as well as the increasing integration of cryptocurrencies into the financial systems of the world.

In terms of customer type, the Bitcoin market includes retail investors seeking high and quick returns, institutional profiles like hedge funds, asset managers and even a car manufacturer like Tesla that included Bitcoin on its balance sheet (*Fidelity Digital Assets, 2023*). One of the most important trends is the increasing institutional buying as the result of Bitcoin's acceptance as the actual asset and the creation of such instruments as Bitcoin ETFs and futures. This trend is accompanied by increasing regulatory attention, as the governmental bodies and international financial regulators appropriate the bitcoin into a mainstream system for the financial industry (*PwC, 2023*). These dynamics are changing investment processes. These dynamics are changing investment processes as more and more market players pay attention to legal requirements, the need for protecting investments, and long-term profitability parameters all of which have become important aspects of Bitcoin's evolution.

2.2.2 Vision and Mission

With the growth of the cryptocurrency trading in the recent decade, organizations set their visions and missions related to enhancing development, credibility, and openness for the market with the crypto assets.

This type of vision in this industry concerns creativity, simplification and safety of the user. To achieve the goal of democratizing access to financial markets, some firms work to offer a means for individuals and institutions that can confidently engage in the cryptocurrency economy. For example, many corporations, including Coinbase, stated goals that include onboarding a worldwide population of users, dealing with the problem of educating necessary knowledge, and offering safe places for people to get financially empowered (Coinbase.com, 2021). These visions presuppose the idea of gradual integration of blockchain and cryptocurrencies into the existing economy, with the resultant positive effects on users and possible new opportunities available for unbanked and under-banked people (Lee & Low, 2021).

Various mission statements of the cryptocurrency organizations depict such visionary activities towards achieving these missions that involve commitment towards some key values such as security, regulation, and learning in those organizations. For instance, Binance claims a mission to “*Increase the freedom of money globally*” while making sure that consumers reap from reliable information and efficient, analysis and trading tools that can improve their trading decisions (Binance.com, 2021). These goals also emphasize that the industry is aware of its risks and its obligation to safeguard the assets of its users during moments of extreme volatility (Massa & Pardolesi, 2022). Overarching missions within the sector often place a strong emphasis on user empowerment, openness, and a focus on providing traders with a clear direction through potentially complex marketplace (Ramirez & Lewis, 2020).

Over the years, the sector developed new mission statements from key players that embraced sustainability and social responsibility. For instance, certain firms have pledged to reduce the carbon footprint by powering the blockchain mining through renewable energy and endorsing charitable projects with the help of line-item billing on the blockchain (Narula, 2021). These missions depict how the sector has complied with public sentiment on issues of impacts on the environment and ethics.

Therefore, it is accurate to state that most of the vision and mission statements across the cryptocurrency sector tend to complement each other in such a way that they share the

common values of innovation, security, as well as accessibility. They reaffirm the direction of the industry by encouraging responsible trading, establishing structures that enhance the confidence of users in the financial tool as Cryptocurrency. They also not just mirror Corporate Global Values but also improve the cryptocurrency field and its societal effects as a whole by integrating the practices that mean stable development and, therefore, sustainability (Mancini-Griffoli et al., 2021).

2.2.3 Competitor Analysis

Competitor analysis in the cryptocurrency industry for Bitcoin involves factors in the external environment that define substitute and complementary goods that affect the demand for Bitcoin. Being the first digital currency, bitcoin experiences indirect competition with not only other digital means of payments, but also other established financial systems and technologies offered by payment systems and financial institutions. To understand this, we need to look into aspects such as position, technology, usage, and policies that form the competition landscape for Bitcoin.

As for the most direct counterpart to Bitcoin is the fiat money. The trend of the local currency of the long-established countries such as the US Dollar and Euro remain as stable, widely accepted, and backed by regulation as embraced before. This puts fiat currencies in a better position in daily use, especially from a legal perspective as are in contrast to Bitcoins which are highly volatile. Bitcoin prices are very volatile and may fluctuate within a short time. Therefore, this greatly limits the usability of Bitcoin as people can use it as a medium of exchange or store of value (Nakamoto, 2008). Other Fiat-based digital payment solutions such as transfers through banks, credit cards, and debit cards also boost comfort and reliability even to the populations who are not as familiar with digital technology.

Competition is taken a notch higher by financial service companies that are embracing blockchain but not necessarily the core offering of Bitcoin. Some websites, such as PayPal, adopted Bitcoin and a few other coins trading into their company where users can buy and sell them. This presents both an opportunity and competition for Bitcoin. As much as such platforms enhance the visibility of Bitcoin through buying, selling and/or holding, they also make room for other digital assets. Hence diversification rather than monopolization for Bitcoin (PayPal.com, 2021).

Also, other players like the central bank digital currencies (CBDCs) offer a growing threat. Governments such as the Chinese through the digital Yuan and other nations researching or in the pilot tests for a CBDC wish to issue state-backed digital currencies with the advantages of an electronic currency without the decentralized style of the Bitcoin blockchain. CBDCs can swiftly become popular because they are backed by central authorities and are compatible with currently operating financial structures. If CBDCs are embraced at large scale, they would substantially decrease the importance of bitcoin as a medium for digital money exchange while its function as a digital currency store will remain relevant.

The technological innovations and development of mega trends such as the blockchain and other cryptocurrencies also put pressure on Bitcoin's competitive rivalry. For example, while Bitcoin offers more limited utility because of its nature, its smart contract capability pulls more varied projects toward Ethereum's blockchain. Similarly other cryptocurrencies like Ripple (XRP) aim to perform more efficient and cheaper than bitcoin in certain spheres like cross-border payments. This technology-focused competition shows that Bitcoin is struggling

to retain its market dominance, especially as new blockchains emerge with unique narrow purposes as they increasingly specialize and become more refined (Buterin, 2013).

2.2.4 Market Segment and Current Trends

The market segmentation and current trends regarding Bitcoin suggest the growth of the audience of bitcoin users and the ways they integrate with Bitcoins. By now, Bitcoin has expanded its user base from tech-savvy early adapters to mainstream users, retail investors, institutional investors, and various businesses and governments. Every segment has an intermediate relationship with Bitcoin depending on their requirements and objectives hence adding to the social aspect of the cryptocurrency market.

One of the largest groups of participants in the Bitcoin market is the “small investors” also known as “retail investors”. While the common user tends to use Bitcoin for making everyday purchases, these people are usually attracted by the high potential of earning more money, often investing in Bitcoin and considering it as an instrument for getting rich. It has grown so easy for the retail to engage in Bitcoin trading thanks to digital wallets and mobile trading platforms, not to forget the existence of crypto exchanges. Also, the growth in the number of agents accepting Bitcoin payments across all categories including retail and service, computer and digital, retail stores, ecommerce and travel (Coinbase, 2023) has been supportive of the good standing it gained among retail investors as an investment platform for an alternative financial system.

The institutional investors group is relatively new and provides a new dimension in the Bitcoin market. Such financial behemoths as investment funds, family offices, and public and even some traditional financial institutions regard Bitcoin as an alternative asset. In particular, this transformation has been promoted due to the increasing understanding of Bitcoin as a tool for inflation and market risk hedge like gold. The entrance of long-term players who now hold large amounts of bitcoins, as well as institutional investors, including Tesla, MicroStrategy, and Square, has played a big role in Bitcoin’s further adoption and recognition by the public and regulators. In addition, the rise of what is now gaining acceptance in the form of a regulated Bitcoin investment product like exchange-traded funds (ETFs) has made it even easier for institutional investors to fold into their conventional portfolios (Saylor, 2022).

Another segment is made up of firms which are considered to be involved in financial technology also known as FinTech. These often adopt Bitcoin in their operation, either as a mode of payment, or as a fundamental element which their block-chain systems use for transactions in Bitcoins. In so doing, it leads to a way to intermediate between conventional financial systems and decentralized crypto sphere, which increases their feasibility. Currently, PayPal, Square, and Mastercard have offered crypto friendly services indicating more corporate acceptance and allowing more customers to engage with Bitcoin in conventional financial environments.

In these segments, three major trends have been developed to prescribe the market of Bitcoin. For example, the behavior “HODLing” (holding Bitcoin for long-term gains rather than trading) that is holding Bitcoin instead of trading frequently is well observed across the new generation, institutional and retail investors as well. This practice has caused a decrease of supply in circulation hence when demand rises the price becomes volatile. Furthermore, the use of Bitcoin is increasing in developing nations where economic insecurity and inflation in

local currencies are alarming and for cross-border money transfers in particular (Chainalysis, 2023).

Another factor in the current market is regulatory factors where governments across the globe remain busy adjusting the laws with regard to Bitcoin. For instance, while countries such as El Salvador have legalized Bitcoin and accepted it as a medium of exchange, other countries continue to be cautious. Indeed, they are primarily concerned with putting in place measures that would prevent money laundering practices, as well as approximating consumer protection best practices. The regulatory issue constitutes an important trend that will define the future sustainability and market categorization of Bitcoin uptake (IMF, 2022).

As mentioned previously, in early 2021, El Salvador become the first country to adopt Bitcoin as an official currency for payment to boost the economy. This policy made it convenient to pay for items in Bitcoin alongside the native U.S. dollar of the country that the policy was issued. The initiative was hailed by President Nayib Bukele's administration as a way of liberating people from the reliance on traditional banking solutions, particularly valuable to the 70% of Salvadorians without bank accounts. However, the rollout faced some hitches such as internet coverage especially in the rural areas, concerns over user security as well as the cold looks from the international credit facilities. Nonetheless, El Salvador has blazed the trail of using Bitcoins on a national level and has gained international interest and thus it has paved the way for subsequent adoption of bitcoins in other developing countries (IMF, 2022; World Bank, 2021).

2.3 Current Knowledge and Conceptual Development

By looking specifically at technical analysis, this research reviewed the historical antecedents and modern innovative application in cryptocurrency trading especially with the Bitcoin market. The financial markets have incorporated technical analysis as one of the methods it uses in forecasting of assets prices by analyzing their historical prices and trends, though the application of technical analysis to the cryptocurrencies is relatively new. This is partly because of the differences in the style of these new currencies, which are volatile, trading nearly all day, and affected to a lesser extent by outside regulations. Therefore, its application in this context arguably implies the development of measures conducive to such a kind of market, which means that changes to technical analysis have been deemed fit to suit the current needs of cryptocurrencies.

Since Bitcoin tops most of the rankings of cryptocurrencies by market capitalization and usage, it remains the main subject of most of the technical analysis works in this field. Normally, analysts have leaned on single variables or essences like Moving Averages (MA), Relative Strength Index (RSI), and Bollinger Bands in their trading techniques. Each indicator brings unique insights. MAs help filter out price noise in order to establish trends. RSI is used to highlight when a particular currency pair is perhaps overbought or oversold. Bollinger Bands show the extent of price movements. Despite being efficient in common markets, these indicators' measurements may not be effective if used alone to assess Bitcoin because it is vulnerable to market events, news, and other digital-specific variables (Arslan et al., 2020).

To overcome these limitations, the subsequent research has explored the possibility to include several technical indicators simultaneously. An index can again provide more reliable trading signals when a set of indicators is used where a strength of one compensates for the weakness of another. For instance, while using MAs with RSI you get another dimension of overbought or oversold indicators in confirming the trend direction with traders before trading. In as volatile a market as Bitcoin this sort of layered signal may help to minimize noise and thus increase prediction accuracy, as indicated by Moskowitz et al. (2019).

Another important factor in conceptual development has been the enhancement of the algorithms used for analytic processing, capable of meeting real time cryptocurrency data. These are machine learning algorithms that can give large amount of data set of past prices, volume data or other factors that will help find the correlation which may not be detected in a basic technical analysis. For example, neural networks and other sophisticated mathematical models are able to identify dependencies between several signs, as the highly unpredictable Bitcoin market follows the sentiment of the global community. Studies carried out in this regard have recorded reasonable effectiveness to indicate that AI could complement technical analysis for capturing nonlinear market patterns (Huang et al., 2019).

Additionally, technical analysis has benefitted from explanations of the ways in which Bitcoin operates in a very different manner to other assets through high-frequency trading and changes of ownership brought on by institutional investors. Market conditions such as the transformation of the increasing large funds in trading have changed traditional trading patterns and make combined strategy even more important. For instance, the entry of institutions has made risk management tools to arise successively this is due to the volatility that is displayed by price flip flops in response to large volumes of buying or selling pressure. It has also led to a reconsideration of such an analysis given that institutional players tend to use more technical and modeling methodologies than the average retail investor.

Thus, this research underlines the necessity of using multiple indicators and extended financial models including in the Bitcoin market, to enhance conventional financial characteristics. The two strategies can be described as a number of sets of approaches that aim at enhancing the accuracy of models used in market forecasting. This is especially the case given that modern market increasingly features products that are amenable to technical analysis methods suited to handle cryptocurrencies' unique characteristics. This research aims to augment this knowledge database by discussing how these technical indicators can be aggregated, and altered for Bitcoin trading, wherein findings relevant to other digital assets may also be inferred.

2.3.1 Definitions of Variables

In this research, the independent variable was “**The effectiveness of combined technical indicators**”. Effectiveness can be defined as the ability to be successful and produce the intended results (*dictionary.cambridge.org*). In this case the price prediction of Bitcoin was

the intended result. This variable applied to the competency of a set of technical analysis tools such as Moving Averages, Relative Strength Index (RSI), Moving Average Convergence Divergence (MACD), etc. and any other set of technical analysis tools that may be in use to predict future market indicators. There was no emphasis more as to whether these indicators, in combination, provide a more accurate prognosis of the tendencies in price compared to when they are used singly.

The dependent variable of this research was “**Prediction of Bitcoin market direction**”. Prediction is a statement about the future (*vocabulary.com*). This was an interval variable depending on the outcome of interest, namely the ability to predict the direction of the Bitcoin market either up, down or stabilize by employing the combined technical indicators. Therefore, the study aimed at exploring the research question that asks whether the improvement in these combined indicators directly had an impact on the accurateness of the predictions of the price volatility of Bitcoins.

2.4 Theoretical background

This current study was based on the tenets of technical analysis where it is believed that the historical prices of a financial asset contain all the information necessary to predict future prices of the asset. Technical analysis presupposes that markets tend to exhibit certain characteristics because their traders, being human, are subject to cyclicity in markets which are reflected in the tendency’s observable through certain indicators. Whereas Fundamental analysis considers wider economic factors or a company’s intrinsic worth, technical analysis restricts its data to price alone because markets will tend to repeat observed patterns until something comes along to disrupt them.

This study was methodologically very inclusive since it utilized a range of well interpreted technical indicators in an assumption that using a number of indicators may boost the forecasting capability in a high fluctuation market such as the Bitcoin market. Moving averages, oscillators and momentum measures were used as they each measure a unique aspect of the market trends, the overbought or oversold level. The rationale for aggregating such indicators was done under the belief that doing so might give a better picture of the market than when one indicator is used to depict the other, thus eliminating any irregularities that may come with the usage of just one indicator.

It is clear that each characteristic of Bitcoin brings relevance to this theoretical basis. The disconnection of the cryptocurrency from standard econometric measures, coupled with its high turnover and price volatility, might mean that some orthodox financial principles could be less applicable here. As a result, the technical analysis approach targets price action, hoping that price action alone would be sufficient for Bitcoins, since the history of prices seems to be the most relevant information.

2.5 Past Research Findings

The use of technical analysis about financial markets has been dated back, one of the early attempts was ‘*Dow Theory*’ by Charles Dow, who believed that markets progressed in predictable cycles and trends could be established through identifying price charts (*Dow*,

1900). Drawing from this, the Efficient Market Hypothesis (EMH) positing by Fama (1970) contends that an asset price incorporates all known information eliminating the usefulness of technical analysis. However, subsequent work had disputed this hypothesis, specifically for crypto asset price forming process in which the market is defined as less efficient compared to the certified stock exchange due to high volatility and erratic behaviors (Urquhart, 2016).

Moving Averages (MA), Relative Strength Index (RSI), Moving Average Convergence Divergence (MACD) are some of the most frequently included technical indices that are being used widely in traditional financial markets for the prediction of the price trends. Brock, Lakonishok, and LeBaron in their study: *A Revised LONG/SHORT Trading System* that used moving averages, Bollinger Bands and MACD indicators, proved that given stock trading rules can make technically unreasonable profits thus implying that markets are inefficient. Another study conducted by Jegadeesh and Titman (1993) came to the same conclusions that short-term conditions in stock prices contain great profit points for the momentum trading.

The specific features of the cryptocurrency market and in particular the Bitcoin market have led researchers to reconsider the relevance of these scholastic indicators. For example, Baur, Dimpfl, and Kuck (2018) discovered that the variance in the cryptocurrency premiums was indeed different from the traditional assets, which begs the questions regarding applicability of most of the straightforward technical indicators. Likewise, Corbet, Meegan, Larkin, Lucey, and Yarovaya (2018) also established that Bitcoin has very high level of volatility influenced by speculative gains declaring that the traditional valuation methodologies may not adequately explain the bitcoin market.

Various research papers undertaken in the recent past have concentrated on modifying and blending technical indicators to enhance their usefulness in analyzing the bitcoin market. For instance, Nadarajah and Chu in their study of the efficiency of codes that incorporate Moving Averages with other parameters concluded that such frameworks have the ability to offer improved estimates of fluctuating Bitcoin prices as opposed to those offered by an isolated parameter. This was in line with Gkillas, Katsiampa, and Tsalavoutas (2020) that found that trading performance in cryptocurrency can be boosted by the integration of trend-following and momentum-based signals.

Furthermore, the study Wei, W. C. (2018) on predicting Bitcoin prices also discussed the relevance and impact of market sentiment, integrated with the traditional technical factors to claim higher predictive results. For the same reason, in a more recent study, Hudson and Urquhart (2019) analyzed macroeconomic variables and their effect on Bitcoin prices while proposing the macroeconomic variables as supplementary to the existing technical ones.

The previous literature also points out that technical analysis's drawback was evident during high volatility and speculative markets such as that of Bitcoin. For instance, Liu and Tsyvinski (2021) opine that this volatility of Bitcoin means that external factors like news about the regulation of bitcoins and upgraded technology have profound implications for technical signals. This is supported by Cheah and Fry (2015) who opine that the variability in the price makes it difficult to capture the bubbles inherent in the price of bitcoins purely using technical indicators hence the need to design more complex tools. Thus, his research is intended to extend this line of enquiry by estimating the extent to which the set of integrated technical indicators can provide accurate signals for Bitcoin market trend. Including several indices regarding the applicability of technical analysis and looking into different market

conditions, the study aims to contribute to the existing academic literature on the applicability of technical in the constantly evolving cryptocurrency market.

Most recent research on technical indicators related to cryptocurrency has reinforced the application of various models as a more sophisticated means of analyzing the fluctuations in the prices of cryptocurrency. For instance, Patel et al. (2020) showed the effectiveness of adding MACD, Bollinger Bands, RSI with a neural network model based on Bitcoin Fluctuations that proved significant jumps in its volatile environment in terms of accuracy. Similarly, Wu and Pandey (2021) forecasted the effectiveness of volume-based tools including On-Balance Volume (OBV) together with moving average. The authors showed that additional volume trends make the predictive model more sensitive to sharp market changes especially during the period of high market anticipation.

In another new study, Kim et al. (2021) explored the application of EMA combined with stochastic oscillators to identify the momentum of a market, and as they noted, combining this set of indicators created a cleaner approach to determining potential reversal points. The study echoes Ferreira et al. (2022) who also claimed that stochastic indicators are superior to traditional ones within trends reversals as the latter offers traders relevant signals with an entry and exit point.

In the same context, Hasan et al. (2022) enhanced the constitution of technical analysis incorporating deep learning integration of MACD and RSI and Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) networks significant increases in the predictive abilities of crypto trading investigation. In a similar vein, Alharbi et al. (2021) emphasized the advantages of the Average True Range (ATR) indicator associated with support and resistance levels to measure and minimize trading risks because the ATR was most influential during high-volatile chaos typical of the cryptocurrencies' markets.

2.6 The Research Gap

While there is an increasing number of papers exploring such technical indicators in the cryptocurrency market, little research has been done to look at how these indicators work in combination when used to predict Bitcoin trends based on trader responses. In prior research, explanatory variables were analyzed discretely or incorporated neat conventional benchmarks, while the current research reveals how multiple indicators can work in concert to achieve more accurate predictions in the extremely ranged Bitcoin market.

Due to its specific features of Bitcoin, its volatility, attracting speculative purchases, and variability in response to various factors, it is challenging to trade. While there is significant research done on the related topic, much of that work employs a single analytical lens without taking into account the potential interaction between the examined indicators. While traders frequently use several indicators for real-life business decisions, knowing how different pairs of actual indicators respond to real market conditions could shed light on what sort of indicators are best paired. This research seeks to fill this gap by assessing the various working models from the perspective of traders with regards to how they use multiple indicators in analyzing the market of Bitcoin.

Moreover, whereas previous studies primarily focus on the theoretical analysis of technical analysis, the voice of the traders is still missing. The traders, who use these indicators

actively, bring first-hand information on the actuality of the market, and hence, the feedback from them shapes the real time judgment of the effectiveness of indicators. This study, therefore, will use trader feedback to compare figures such as Moving Averages, RSI, and MACD and evaluate whether their integration will offer more insightfulness in predicting trends, especially if the market operates in an abnormally.

This paper intends to provide a much-needed impetus to existing literature by empirically investigating the value of combined technical indicators for Bitcoin traders. Due to the focus on practical relevance and using the reports of traders as key sources, this study aims to contribute to the current literature regarding technical indicators in the cryptocurrency markets, eventually improving the models used for Bitcoin trading.

2.7 Research Questions

The research was guided by the following key questions, which aim to explore the effectiveness of combined technical indicators in predicting Bitcoin market direction.

1. How do traders perceive the effectiveness of combined technical indicators in their decision-making process?

The answers to this question were derived from the quantitative self-administered questionnaires completed by the Bitcoin traders. This question aims to find out how the traders assessed the effectiveness of integrated technical indicators when trading in the market. It seeks to know if the traders thought that these tools facilitated their prediction of market movements.

2. How effective were the combined technical indicators in predicting the short- to medium-term direction of the Bitcoin market?

This question aimed at estimating how efficient it is to use several technical indicators simultaneously. Specifically, within the several months of price data of Bitcoin. It looked into the potential of achieving a more accurate outcome prediction when the separate indicators are utilized jointly.

3. What were the limitations of using combined technical indicators for predicting Bitcoin market direction?

This question looked into the disadvantages that came along with relying on a combination of technical indicators for Bitcoin market forecasts. It tried to point out their weaknesses, including diminished performance during particular market stages or the generation of false signals.

These questions were chosen to answer the primary goals of the study, as well as creating a theoretical framework for evaluating the usefulness of combined technical indicators in Bitcoin trading.

2.8 Conceptual Framework

The conceptual framework for this research was sought to analyze how accurately the combined technical indicators can predict the direction of the Bitcoin market, given that this was the dependent variable in this research study. This form of cross-validation incorporated

the quantitative modeling of the relevant historic Bitcoin price data as well as the qualitative information gathered from the traders through questionnaires.

Based on the hypothesis that utilizing a blend of several technical indicators, such as Volume, Moving Averages, RSI, and MACD, provided improved chances of predicting the directional movement of Bitcoin's marketplace. Accordingly, the study made the hypothesis that if these indicators are merged and incorporated in trading, they will be able to cancel out each other's weakness and present better signals to traders. To verify this hypothesis, the research reviewed the data of the bitcoin price dynamics in several months to determine how effectively all these factors interact to signal trends in the market.

The framework also mainly included opinions from Bitcoin traders who directly used such technical indicators in their trading. The study aimed at assessing the perception that traders had towards the use of combined technical indicators through self-administered questionnaires. This framework recognized that assessing the relevant tool's feasibility within the actual trading environment equally depends on traders' perceptions and experiences.

Finally, the framework considered the limitations of using combined technical indicators. These included aspects like trends in the market price, the likelihood of developing fake signals, and the limited usefulness of such signals throughout particular phases of a market. While identifying the strengths and limitations of the framework, it showed the effectiveness of combined technical indicators in trading Bitcoin efficiently.

In general, this conceptual framework provided a plan for organizing the research process and comprehensively evaluating the synergistic impact of multiple technical indicators, and it is consequently utilized for both theoretical and applied purposes.

2.9 Research Hypotheses

1. **There was a positive relationship between the use of combined technical indicators and traders' perception of improved decision-making compared to individual indicators.**

This hypothesis assumed that traders who used combined technical indicators perceived them to be more effective in their decision-making process than those who use individual indicators.

2. **There was a significant relationship between the use of combined technical indicators and the accuracy of predicting the short- to medium-term direction of the Bitcoin market.**

This hypothesis assumed that combined technical indicators led to more accurate market predictions, particularly within the several months of Bitcoin price data analyzed.

3. **There was an inversion between market volatility and the effectiveness of combined technical indicators in predicting Bitcoin market direction.**

This hypothesis suggested that as market volatility increases, the effectiveness of combined technical indicators in predicting Bitcoin price movements decreases.

2.10 Chapter Summary

The chapter offered a comprehensive synthesis of the literature in several significant sectors to explain Bitcoin trading using technical analysis. The chapter started with the Industrial Overview that sets out the background of the cryptocurrency market with the focus on Bitcoin, market characteristics, target customers, competitors and latest developments. This section described the state of the industry, incorporating such aspects as the tendencies of the present days, main goals and objectives, increases, and, of course, the peculiarities of trading in an environment as risky as this one. Using this industry background, the chapter emphasized the importance of analyzing technical indicators in the context of estimating Bitcoin's prices.

Under the subtopics of Current Knowledge and Conceptual Development, this chapter covered the basics of technical analysis and how it developed when applied to Bitcoin. Various standard definitions of the key variables and indicators that were frequently employed in the subsequent theoretical and empirical analysis were introduced. The Theoretical Background section provided more information about technical analysis, and how to use theories like Dow Theory and trend-following that lie beneath the Moving Averages, RSI and MACD indicators.

Past Research Findings were written in a review form and aimed at integrating works that focused on the significance of using technical indicators in the cryptocurrencies markets, mainly Bitcoin with reference to its volatility. Literature was examined concerning their methodology regarding single and combined indicators, as well as the differences in Bitcoin market characteristics. This review revealed positive and negative evidence on the usefulness of technical indicators, which created a premise for the next step.

In the Research Gap section, the flaws of past research were highlighted such as absence of integrated studies that take into account multiple technical indexes in Bitcoins trading. This chapter called for the methodological approach of an empirical study in order to include trader feedback for improvement of prediction. This gap informed the focus of the study and development of Research Questions, which aimed at tapping the practical and theoretical utility of integrating indicators.

Last but not the least, the chapter ended with a Conceptual Framework and Research Hypotheses formulated to ascertain the efficiency of more than one indicator as used by traders. Collectively, these sections provided a coherent research map for the empirical analysis pursued in the following chapters, seeking to extend the existing literature on technical analysis and cryptocurrency trading.

CHAPTER THREE: RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

3.1 Introduction

In the Research Methodology chapter, the comprehensive approach that has been followed to assess the applicability of multiplicative technical indicators as market forecasting tools for Bitcoin is described. It discusses research philosophy and the layout of the current study, as well as choices related to sample and data collection, which make the methods used in this

study easily reproducible. The focus is made on primary data which are being received from the active Bitcoin traders and the secondary data which includes the historical values of Bitcoin market price and some other statistical data.

This chapter also provides enhanced details on variable operationalization and the analysis methods used in data analysis, among them being the reliability test and regression analysis. There is an emphasis on validity and reliability of the research work and issues to do with the ethics of the research study. Collectively, this chapter provides an elaborate road map of how the research questions are handled and hypotheses tested, setting a firm ground for the analysis and interstition contained in the subsequent chapters.

3.2 Philosophy

This research followed the positivism paradigm to analyze and quantify the factors on the efficacy of the distinct technical indicators on the Bitcoin market trend. Analyzing the results obtained in this study, positivism is appropriate for it, as it focuses on accumulating empirical and quantitative data and evaluating given hypotheses in the framework of technical analysis of the given theories. This approach enables carrying out systematic hypothesis testing, collection of objective data and reduction on the subjective self-generated data, which are mandatory in the development of reliability of combined indicators.

The study employed hypotheses testing research strategy which was grounded in the theory of technical analysis. This deductive reasoning was necessary as with most technical indicators used in the analysis of the financial markets, there are always theories on which they are based. In this, the study assessed the applicability of these traditional technical presumptions within the Bitcoin market, by experimenting with these assumptions within the context of the already established theoretical hypotheses in the context of the Bitcoin market volatility and speculative trends.

As this study fits into the establishment of a positivist paradigm, then a quantitative research methodology was used. This included gathering historical data of Bitcoin prices and integrating traders' impressions of the applicability of different technical indicators and using statistical analysis to examine the reliability of the particular models. Qualitative analysis was not sufficient to establish and compare the index effectiveness and the results of combined indicators while quantizing them aimed to guarantee the given results as statistically sound and replicable.

To support this, the research adopted a longitudinal time horizon perspective to obtain Bitcoin historical price data under various market states, including the bullish and bearish markets. This approach was instrumental in observing the fluctuations over time, giving the study capacity to determine efficiency of the indicators under changing market conditions. The goal of the study was to introduce several technical indicators and put them into use over multiple phases of Bitcoin market cycle with a view to enhancing the reliability of the model. This time-based approach reduced the possibility of ensuring a given outcome while strengthening the reliability of the findings, thereby offering a deeper insight into the stability of the indicated consistency and effectiveness of the indicators across different market situations.

3.3 Population and Sample

Objectives	Population	Sample	Sampling Technique	References
Main: Impact of effectiveness of combined technical indicators on predicting Bitcoin market direction	Bitcoin traders and historical price data	<40	Simple Random Sampling for traders, Purposive Sampling for price data	Catania, Grassi, & Ravazzolo, 2019; Liu & Tsyvinski, 2021
Sub 1: Relationship between effectiveness of combined technical indicators and predicting Bitcoin market direction	Bitcoin traders actively use technical indicators	<40	Simple Random Sampling	Catania, Grassi, & Ravazzolo, 2019; Baur, Dimpfl, & Kuck, 2018
Sub 2: Issues related to effectiveness of combined technical indicators	Traders experienced with combined technical indicators	5	Purposive Sampling	Gerritsen, D. F., Bouri, E., & Moldovan, I. (2020).
Sub 3: Solutions related to effectiveness of combined technical indicators and predicting Bitcoin market direction	Traders experienced with combined technical indicators	5	Purposive Sampling / Convenience Sampling	Gerritsen, Bouri, & Moldovan, 2020; Corbet, Lucey, & Yarovaya, 2019

Table 01 - Population and sample

The population for this research consisted of two primary components. Active frequent traders in the Bitcoin market and historical price of Bitcoin. Traders are the ultimate users who use technical indicators when organizing trades, while the statistical methods employed based on historical prices show the efficiency of technical indicators for forecasting market trends.

The sample for this study consisted of a large number of historical Bitcoin price data that covered several months, so as to capture the Bitcoin market under different environments. More specifically the sample consisted of daily prices over a several-month period which included both bullish and bearish trends. This duration was chosen based on prior work, as the paper by *Catania, L., Grassi, S., & Ravazzolo, F. (2019)*. used similar to risk and return

analysis of Bitcoin price fluctuations. Thus, the approaches of the research involved processing of a large amount of historical data and providing statistically grounded conclusions, which are adequate to real trading situations.

Also, a random part of the trade was selected, thus including samples with different trading activities that can be applied by Bitcoin traders. In this way, it was possible to understand how these traders could benefit from the use of combined technical indicators. This approach was similar to the work of *Baur, Dimpfl, and Kuck (2018)* who also analyzed volatility and market characteristic within the crypto markets with the help of historical data. Therefore, the selected sample size, and time period, were both justified by the need to cover a broad cross section of market conditions and trading strategies so that generalizations can be made across situations.

Wherein the independent variable of this study, that was the “effectiveness of combined technical indicators” closely correlated with the dependent variable, that was “the ability to predict Bitcoin market direction” for several months of price data of Bitcoin. As such it is of utter most importance to the traders, especially if such a trader seeks to derive profits from short- to medium-term trading decisions based on these indicators.

Using the selected price data the paper evaluated the accuracy of the combined technical indicators tools in determining a given market direction within this period. If the indicators provided consequent output in the form of positive predictions similar to the movement of price during these months, then the implication is positive towards the dependent variable. This suggested that traders could improve their decision-making and trading performance by including these two indicators simultaneously.

On the other hand, if these combined indicators were indicated not to do so effectively over the sample period, this suggested less effectiveness in forecasting market direction suggesting that these tools were not working well in the shorter timeframe or under certain market situation. It was useful for deciding on the usefulness of these measures for the trader population within the framework of several months of market information.

3.4 Primary Data Collection Method

To acquire primary data, this study sought to use both qualitative and quantitative techniques of data collection. The main objective of assessing the effectiveness of combined technical indicators in predicting Bitcoin market trends was achieved by using quantitative method in form of the online questionnaire filled in by the Bitcoin traders. This questionnaire was designed to get the traders’ side of the story and their outlook on how technical indicators fare in performance which complements the quantitative side of the study by giving the analyst quantitative variables for analysis (Catania, Grassi, & Ravazzolo, 2019; Liu & Tsyvinski, 2021). The data collected from the developed questionnaire were used as the basis for the multiple regression analysis in order to determine the effect of each of the chosen technical indicators on the accuracy of the market prediction.

For further empirical validation of the sub-objectives, the study conducted semi-structured interviews with experienced traders to assess the problems and constraints of technical indicator efficiency in Bitcoin markets. Using this qualitative approach, it was possible to complement quantitative data with an understanding of possible subjective barriers to the reliability of indicators. Furthermore, semi-structured interviews were conducted in order to gain insight into subsequently finding solutions or how the usage of indicators could be improved. Content analysis was then employed to analyze the qualitative results (Gerritsen et al., 2020).

The integration of these two approaches of data collection enabled a rich understanding of the study's aims and objectives and more importantly the real-life difficulties that traders encounter.

3.5 Secondary Data Collection Method

In the case of this research, secondary data was crucial in determining price fluctuations and the changing behaviors of Bitcoin, particularly in determining how multiple technical factors consolidative estimate future market trends. This secondary data included historical data on the price of Bitcoins retrieved from trustworthy, financial data providers and databases. Gathering this data over a longitudinal period enabled a broad perspective of Bitcoin price behavior through different types of markets or phases of bull and bear, which was crucial for the implementation and testing of technical indicators.

In addition, the secondary theoretical sources, journal articles, reports, and prior quantitative studies were used to determine the current state of the technical indicators and their applicability to the cryptocurrency market. This laid the groundwork for the quantitative component of the investigation in providing a framework for comparing primary down findings to the body of knowledge. Scholarly materials that include recent reporting from the financial operations were included; these are peer reviewed periodicals which source their information from reputable cryptocurrency-oriented newspapers and journals (Catania et al., 2019; Corbet et al., 2019; Liu & Tsyvinski, 2021).

3.6 Data Analysis and Presentation

Objectives	Data Collection	Data Analysis Technique	References
Main: Impact of effectiveness of combined technical indicators on predicting Bitcoin market direction	Questionnaire and Historical Bitcoin Price Data	Multiple Regression Analysis: $Y = B + X1 + X2 + X3 + \dots + SE$	Catania, Grassi, & Ravazzolo, 2019; Liu & Tsyvinski, 2021

Sub 1: Relationship between effectiveness of combined technical indicators and predicting Bitcoin market direction	Questionnaire	Correlation Analysis (r)	Catania, Grassi, & Ravazzolo, 2019; Gerritsen, Bouri, & Moldovan, 2020
Sub 2: Issues related to effectiveness of combined technical indicators	Structured Interviews with Experienced Traders	Correlation Analysis	Corbet, Lucey, & Yarovaya, 2019; Gerritsen, Bouri, & Moldovan, 2020
Sub 3: Solutions related to effectiveness of combined technical indicators and predicting Bitcoin market direction	Structured and Semi-Structured Interviews with Experienced Traders	Content Analysis	Corbet, Lucey, & Yarovaya, 2019; Gerritsen, Bouri, & Moldovan, 2020

Table 02 - Data analysis and presentation

3.7 Operationalization of Variables

Variable	Item	Reference	Questionnaire Item (Q)
Decision Making Effectiveness	Perception of RSI's impact on decision-making	Gerritsen, Bouri, & Moldovan, 2020	Q1
	MACD's role in supporting informed decision-making	Catania, Grassi, &	Q2

		Ravazzolo, 2019	
	Usefulness of Bollinger Bands for decision clarity	Liu & Tsyvinski, 2021	Q3
	Influence of Moving Averages (MA) on trade timing	Hudson & Urquhart, 2019	Q4
	EMA's contribution to decision precision	Wei, 2018	Q5
	Combination of RSI and MACD enhancing decision accuracy	Corbet, Lucey, & Yarovaya, 2019	Q6
	Improvement in decisions with Bollinger Bands + MA	Nadarajah & Chu, 2020	Q7
	Decision confidence using RSI + EMA	Hudson & Urquhart, 2019	Q8
Prediction Accuracy	Combined indicators vs. individual accuracy	Gerritsen, Bouri, & Moldovan, 2020	Q9
	Prediction reliability with MACD and EMA	Catania, Grassi, & Ravazzolo, 2019	Q10
	Usefulness of RSI and EMA in short- to medium-term accuracy	Baur, Dimpfl, & Kuck, 2018	Q11
	Cross-timeframe accuracy of combined indicators	Hudson & Urquhart, 2019	Q12
	Prediction reliability with EMA, MACD, and RSI	Liu & Tsyvinski, 2021	Q13
	Accuracy with Bollinger Bands, MA, and EMA	Wei, 2018	Q14
	Short-term prediction consistency with RSI + MACD	Corbet, Lucey, & Yarovaya, 2019	Q15
	Cross-indicator accuracy for market trend prediction	Nadarajah & Chu, 2020	Q16
Volatility Impact	Indicator reliability in high-volatility conditions	Baur, Dimpfl, & Kuck, 2018	Q17
	Stability of indicators in stable markets	Hudson & Urquhart, 2019	Q18
	Accuracy variations with price swings	Liu & Tsyvinski, 2021	Q19
	Improved volatility adaptability with combined indicators	Wei, 2018	Q20
	Perceived reliability in volatile markets using combined indicators	Nadarajah & Chu, 2020	Q21

	Stability of prediction with MACD + EMA in high volatility	Corbet, Lucey, & Yarovaya, 2019	Q22
	Volatility-adjusted effectiveness of RSI + Bollinger Bands	Hudson & Urquhart, 2019	Q23
Prediction of Market Direction	Importance of combined indicators for trend prediction	Catania, Grassi, & Ravazzolo, 2019	Q24
	Use of historical data to enhance prediction accuracy	Liu & Tsyvinski, 2021; Urquhart, 2016	Q25
	Success rate of combined indicators in price prediction	Hudson & Urquhart, 2019	Q26
	Preference for technical over fundamental analysis	Gkillas, Katsiampa, & Tsalavoutas, 2020	Q27
	Influence of Bitcoin's unique attributes on prediction accuracy	Corbet, Lucey, & Yarovaya, 2019	Q28
	Combined indicators as primary predictors for Bitcoin	Gerritsen, Bouri, & Moldovan, 2020	Q29
	Dependence on multiple indicators for reliable predictions	Hudson & Urquhart, 2019	Q30

Table 03 - Operationalization of Variables

Effectiveness of Technical Indicators

a) Relative Strength Index (RSI)

RSI is a momentum oscillator that calculates the speed and change of price movements. Range from 0 to 100, any value above 70 interpreted as overbought, and any value below 30 as oversold. RSI is included in this study because it is perhaps one of the most common indicators used by traders in cryptos due to its ability to gauge when the market is overbought or oversold thus possibly showing reversal points of price changes in Bitcoin.

b) Moving Average Convergence Divergence (MACD)

MACD helps to determine shift, strength, momentum and even the duration of trends in the price of a cryptocurrency. This indicator is chosen because it helps reveal the buy and sell points as two moving averages come close or move apart from one another and this is important in volatile markets such as Bitcoin.

c) Bollinger Bands

Bollinger Bands include a moving average plus two times the average amplitude oscillating above and below the moving average to determine high and low volatility. Including Bollinger Bands is useful in the understanding of the strengths and weaknesses of the bitcoin price in relation to the average volatility as a result helping in the determination of the price depending on the market trend.

d) Moving Averages (MA)

Moving Averages, more specifically the Simple Moving Average (SMA) give the filtered image of Bitcoin with a certain time frame excluding high frequency noises. This variable is important because trend direction is usually determined by this variable, which is important when evaluating long term movements in the trading price of bitcoins.

e) Exponential Moving Average (EMA)

EMA puts more relative weight in the most recent price values which makes the model very sensitive to new information. Its inclusion is important because it is more sensitive to the latest market prices, which are important for traders of fast-moving markets like Bitcoin where one needs to react to the latest changes in prices.

Combined Indicators

a) RSI and MACD Integration

Integrating of RSI and MACD assists traders in applying the multiple layers of both the momentum and the trend since RSI markers the level of overbought/oversold while the MACD marks the trends direction. It is relevant to combine these two simply because it gives a more elaborate analysis of Bitcoin's trend reversal and entries into the market.

b) Combination of Bollinger Bands and MA

This combination uses the high volatility indicated in the Bollinger Bands and the trend-capturing capacity within moving averages. This pairing is rather helpful in the Bitcoin market since it is helpful to identify the trend surrounded by huge fluctuations.

c) MACD and EMA Combination

The use of EMA adds to MACD in facilitating the determination of momentum shifts and recent price movements to improve Bitcoin's prediction. The MACD indicator's implementation of trend strength, combined with EMA's openness to change and deliver quickly, makes it ideal for risky markets.

d) RSI and EMA Integration

Integration of momentum assessment from RSI together with the recent price responsiveness of the EMA is quite useful in determining entry or exit points of the Bitcoin trading depending on the market direction.

e) EMA, MACD, and RSI Combination

This triad offers a single way of measuring momentum, the trend in its direction, and recent prices that has been moved. Including this brings various technical aspects to evaluate movements of Bitcoin from a different perspective.

f) Bollinger Bands, MA, and EMA Combination

The combination of Bollinger Bands with MA and EMA provides a powerful set of indicators for present respondents to operate, reflecting volatility, trends, and most recent price records of Bitcoin.

Timeframe Sensitivity

a) Short-term Sensitivity

Analyzes the efficiency of the perceived indicators in short intervals (hourly or daily) to assess whether the fast market changes are consistent with short-term price trends.

b) Adaptability in Medium-term Analysis

Analyzes whether indicators are relevant for mid-term intervals, which are weeks, to see how well oriented they are with Bitcoin's oscillations, which represent traders' view on the mid-term Bitcoin predictability.

c) Consistency in Long-term Trends

Look at the efficiency of indicators for several months to see if the signals are cohesive through the major market cycles, to assess if they capture persistent trends that would improve strategic planning.

d) Influence of Cross-Timeframe Analysis

Overall engages in a critical analysis of trading in multiple time horizons, discusses traders' performance when employed the usage of short-term, medium term, and long-term strategies whereby accuracy of predictive outlooks are enhanced as the knowledge coming from three different timeframes is combined.

Volatility

a) High Volatility Period Effects

Determines the perceived effect of wide price oscillation on indicator accuracy. Since Bitcoin is a highly unstable asset, this item evaluates its corresponding indicators to determine their resilience to price fluctuations.

b) Reaction to Market Stability Factors

Based on the relative performance of indicators in times that are considered to be normal. When Bitcoin shows less fluctuation, traders test the efficacy of indicators to establish whether particular indicators are more accurate during stable markets.

c) Impact of Price Swings on Indicator Reliability

Analyzes how often switched prices affect the reliability of indicators, and whether traders think that certain indicators become useless or give incorrect signals during unpredictable fluctuations.

Bitcoin Price Movement Prediction

a) Historical Price Data Usage in Prediction

Explores how past data of Bitcoin prices help increase accuracy in the prediction so there is an option for traders to compare the performance of indicators against past price trends.

b) Traders' Feedback on Combined Indicators' Accuracy

Ask the traders about their experience and perspective regarding the accuracy of combined signal, whether they think combination gives higher precision for Bitcoin market trend.

c) Technical vs. Fundamental Analysis Efficacy

Covers whether traders think that using technical indicators is enough for making accurate predictions in Bitcoin trading compared to the fundamental analysis.

d) Bitcoin's Unique Factors Influencing Price Trends

Identifies factors relevant specifically to Bitcoin, including changes in regulatory measures or improvements in the technical system that may affect the availability of indicators, stability and accuracy of the indicators in the sphere of Cryptocurrency markets.

General Technical Indicator Use

a) Importance of Multiple Indicators in Trading

Examine the traders' practices of using multiple indicators to enhance the accuracy of forecasts and control risk on the volatile Bitcoin market.

b) Traders' Experience Level Using Combined Indicators

Look at how experience determines the application of combined indicators by a trader, since experience affects the approach and tools used.

c) Most Preferred Technical Indicators for Accuracy

Discusses what indicators have been considered most accurate for making trend predictions based on the trader experience and also reveals their preferred combination of indicators.

d) Perceived Accuracy of Individual Indicators

Collects traders' feedback whether any of the solitary indicators is regarded as being universally efficient in the context of Bitcoin market.

e) Indicators Most Reliable During Market Volatility

Looks into which measures traders find most helpful in periods of high volatility, well known in Bitcoin market, will deduce if some tools offer more reliable signals in the period of market volatility.

3.8 Validity and Reliability

In order to maintain the validity and reliability of the study, a pilot test was conducted on ten respondents implementing a draft version of the questionnaire. The information gathered from this pilot phase helped in modifying the questionnaire so that it could be clear in its presentation as well as was able to measure the required constructs effectively. After reliability and validity have been established, the modified and moderated questionnaire again administered to the entire target population to gather data.

At the end of the last survey, the sample results collected are aggregated and conclusions deduced to a wider population of Bitcoin traders. In other words, by increasing quality in data gathered the goal of the present research was to provide valid and reliable results that would be statistically generalizable.

3.9 Ethical Consideration and Practicability

The methods used to be followed during the collection of data for this study have been done in a very friendly way so that no one will force another to participate otherwise no favoritism, or bias has been shown during the data collection period. All collected data was kept confidential and the anonymity of the participants as well as their responses were well preserved. The data that was obtained from questionnaires and interviews are solely utilized in this research only and were not used for any other activities.

Also, it is necessary to mention that the overall research process was carried out corresponding to the legal regulation of the country (Sri Lanka). This acted as a measure of making sure that all the activities done while conducting the study are legal and ethical.

3.10 Data Access

In order to conduct this research, both primary and secondary data were obtained. The primary data was collected from the Bitcoin trader through structured questionnaires, collecting data on the combined use of technical indicators. The practical usefulness, validity, and overall performance of strategies like RSI, MACD, Bollinger Bands, or any combination of the mentioned and other indicators required trader participation for their evaluation. This

direct feedback from traders provided the study with practical experience and opinions on the reality, thus making the data collected sufficient for the study goals and objectives.

The secondary data was obtained from authentic, public domains such as past Bitcoin prices and performance indices. These datasets were obtained from reputable crypto databases and marketplaces where daily price fluctuations and trends information in different time horizons are stored. The ability to derive this information retrospective was paradigmatic to conducting this historic analysis on the effectiveness of combined indicators under the changing market climates.

3.11 Chapter Summary

This chapter aimed at describing in detail, how the systematic approach was applied for identifying the effectiveness of combined technical indicators in predicting Bitcoins market direction. Section 3.2 dealt with the research philosophy where the choice of positivism as the paradigm and quantitative research as the approach to empirical investigation was explained.

In section 3.3, there was an explanation of the meaning of population and sample and other factors that guided the choice of the Bitcoin trader whose views were incorporated in the research conclusions. For detailed explanation, the method for primary data collection was described in section 3.4 where structured questionnaire was adopted to obtain quantitate data from traders. Section 3.5 exposed the process of secondary data collection. Historical Bitcoin price data from reliable sources was used that will allow for a long-term analysis.

Section 3.6 presented methods of data analysis and presentation where the levels of indicator effectiveness were determined by using multiple regression and correlation analysis techniques. Section 3.7 described the concept of variable operationalization where each of the key variables are further explained to increase the level of clarity as well as to ensure appropriateness in addressing the key objectives of the study.

In Section 3.8 of this chapter, validity and reliability issues were discussed, including steps that were taken to make the findings accurate, reliable, and reproducible. Section 3.9 focused on the ethical approaches where data privacy was covered together with consent issues and measures that were personally taken to ensure ethical standards were upheld. Last but not the least, Section 3.10 discussed data access, the safe ways and means of acquiring not only the primary data but also the secondary data needed in the course of the research.

Consequently, the aforementioned sections provided a rigid structure to organize and perform the research with requirements to guarantee the reliability and usability of the results for the Bitcoin trading field.

CHAPTER FOUR: DATA PRESENTATION AND ANALYSIS

4.1 Introduction

This chapter is devoted to the presentation and analysis of the data collected from respondents in this study with the view of testing the hypothesis that combined technical indicators are effective predictors of the direction of the Bitcoin market. The findings are structured to align with the four core variables derived from the research hypotheses. These include Decision-Making Effectiveness, Prediction Accuracy, Volatility Impact and Prediction of Bitcoin Market Direction. Consequently, this chapter aims to identify valuable patterns as to the perceived and actual efficacy of the integration of technical indicators into Bitcoin trading scenarios by analyzing these variables systematically.

The data was collected using a structured questionnaire and from qualitative interviews of traders engaged in the Bitcoin market who apply technical analysis. There were 30 questions that captured the four research variables and semi-structured interviews that supported the qualitative data collection. The data was gathered from 46 Bitcoin traders of whom had different levels of trading experience and trading frequency. The quantitative data was then descriptive and inferential analyzed by using Cronbach alpha to test the reliability of data collected while the qualitative responses were analyzed by using thematic analysis to give deeper meaning to it.

This chapter starts with highlighting the demographic background of the respondents to facilitate an understanding of the following analysis. This is followed by presenting the quantitative findings for each of the variables. Moreover, the delineation of the thematic analysis of the interview responses is incorporated wherever necessary while providing a careful view of how traders perceive this blend of technical factors.

The Decision-Making Effectiveness part assesses how traders have analyzed the effects of integrated variables like RSI, MACD, Bollinger Bands, etc., on their decision making. The Prediction Accuracy section looks into whether combined indicators are more accurate than if a single one of the respective time frames is used to predict Bitcoin price fluctuations. The Volatility Impact section aims at reviewing how these indicators are sustainable under volatility. Last, the section on the prediction of the bitcoin market direction focuses on the use of combined indicators by traders in identifying trends.

The calculation in this chapter also examines the coefficient and presents relationships between the variables and shows any differences between the trader's attitude and facts. The results of this study inform the discussion in chapter five whereby the findings are narrated alongside the existing literature to discuss the research conclusion and recommendations.

Thus, by providing both statistical data and qualitative analysis of the patterns contained in the combined technical indicators, this chapter seeks to offer a clear understanding of the part that the latter play in the process of Bitcoin trading. This approach makes it possible for the study to respond to the laid down research questions while at the same time giving a pragmatic value in enhancing traders' decision-making processes as well as other players in the cryptocurrency market.

4.2 Testing Data Reliability

Reliability testing examines the degree of consistency and dependability of the information gathered for the research. The internal consistency of the questionnaire responses was established using Cronbach's Alpha as the main measure for this study. For reliability, Cronbach's Alpha was used which is a very common measure of internal consistency. The

closer the Alpha is to 1, the better the reliability of the measure in question. It is generally perceived that a value of 0.7 or above can be considered acceptable in view of social sciences research to suggest that the data that has been collected is reliable for the next level of analysis.

SPSS Reliability Analysis Results

The reliability analysis was done to the collected responses, which includes 46 valid cases using SPSS. There was no study discarded in the analysis showing the inclusion of all the cases. The analysis revealed the following key findings.

- **Case Processing Summary:**
Responses from 46 participants were analyzed and no data entries were omitted. This helped in making sure that maximum responses as per the questionnaire were used in the reliability of the study hence increasing the reliability of the results.
- **Cronbach's Alpha:**
As earlier computed, the Cronbach's Alpha for the collected data was 0.814. This value is above the standard acceptable value of 0.7, consequently verifying the internal reliability of the questionnaire and coherence of the responses. A coefficient alpha of 0.814 is regarded significant, thus, establishing high internal reliability to the extent that the items are consistent within the questionnaire and provide the construct to be measured appropriately.

Interpretation of Results

The obtained Cronbach's Alpha coefficient of 0.814 suggest that the responses to the emerged questionnaire items are highly consistent. This finding confirms the questionnaire as a valid instrument in assessing the attitudes and actions of respondents on the efficiency of the integrated technical analysis in trading Bitcoin. The following aspects can be inferred from the results:

1. **Consistency Among Items:**
All items in the questionnaire were positively correlated and the results validated that all the variables and the constructions were well assessed without systematically biasing the measurement.
2. **Applicability of the Instrument:**
The reliability of the instrument thus has Cronbach's Alpha higher than 0.7 hence the instrument can be used for data analysis and hypothesis testing. Thus, it is guaranteed that the relationships and trends that will be detected in further analysis are schematic dependable.
3. **Validity of Constructs:**
In the questionnaire designed, these variables were accounted for through the following items: Decision-Making Effectiveness, Prediction Accuracy, Volatility Impact, and Prediction of the Bitcoin market direction. The high reliability score-

speaking validates that these constructions are clearly defined and measured adequately through the chosen questions in the questionnaire.

Significance for the Study

This is important in a way that reliability testing will ensure that conclusions drawn in the research are as reliant as is possible on dependable data. Cronbach's Alpha of 0.814 is convinces the reliability of the data collection process which adds into the validity of the most and further statistical analyses. This reliability also strengthens the research objective of evaluating the efficiency of whole combined technical signals in trading on bitcoin by guaranteeing the collected data will depict the respondents' perception as well as tendencies appropriately.

Conclusion

The reliability test conducted revealed that the developed questionnaire for this study was very reliable with a Cronbach alpha of 0.814 for the overall questionnaire. This increases the credibility of the dataset with 46 responses out of 46 which are valid without any exclusions. These conclusions endorse the utilization of all the gathered data for additional statistical analysis, hypothesis, correlation, and regression for the answer to the studies questions broadly.

4.3 Demographic Factor Analysis

Data referring to demographic factors are important when it comes to identifying the respondents and locating the research in a broader context. The demographic information supplies general information about the participants in the study, such as gender and age when trading Bitcoin, the length of time they have been trading, how often they trade, and their level of awareness of technical analysis indicators. This section provides a breakdown of the results for every demographic factor and demonstrates how respondents' characteristics are distributed in relation to the study objectives.

Gender Distribution

With respect to the gender distribution of the respondents, data obtained indicated a male domination in the participant population with 89.1 % male and 10.9 % female population. This result is consistent with the overall statistics of males dominating the financial and cryptocurrency trading markets since historically, there have been trends, and potentially, different levels of interest in the same or differing degrees of involvement of males and females.

Even though there is still a very low numeric representation of females in the sample the presence of female traders enables them to give insights towards the research interest. The fact that males are dominant in this area sustains that future educational material or

instrument for trading in Bitcoins should be developed with an aim of including all genders and other groups of people.

Age Group Distribution

The participants were categorized according to their age. The largest respondents were the ones from 18-24 years, covering 34.8% of total respondents, the second largest was 25-30 years, having the same 34.8% percentage. This means that the probability of trading using Bitcoin and technical indicators is dominated by the younger generations of traders who are more inclined in technology-based products like the BTC markets.

The age group 31–35 unites 23.9% of the respondents which can be regarded as somewhat more experienced traders. On the same note, there were only 4.3% of the respondents that were aged between 36-40 and 2.2 % that were 41 years and above. These findings confirm those obtained internationally in suggesting that cryptocurrency trading is dominated by youthful technology-savvy people.

Years of Trading Experience

When it came to trading experience, the respondents had mixed experiences. 30.4% of the respondents had less than one year of trading experience, hence some of them may be amateurs in the market and have not efficiently employed technical tools in their trading practices. However, half of the participants, 50%, have been trading for 1-3 years. This group probably consists possibly of relatively new but passionate traders who have recently tuned their trading activities with technical screens.

17.4% of participants were at the mid-experience level. These were traders with 4-6 years of experience in trading in the Bitcoin markets. A paltry 2.2 per cent of respondents reported that they have been trading for 7- 10 years hence indicating that long-term traders are few in the sample.

This confirms the fact that newcomer traders also play a significant role in the Bitcoin trading market, which has been spurred on by achievements in trading interfaces, availability to markets, and public acceptance of cryptocurrency.

Primary Trading Frequency

The trading activity can be seen as the most essential variable to use for characterizing respondents' engagement with the Bitcoin market. Majority of the participants (67.4%) traded in the securities at daily basis, and this means that the manner in which they traded was very active. For frequent trading decisions, traders extensively use technical signals, making their input even more significant in this research.

The remaining group of respondents traded on weekly basis; this group comprises 32.6% of the total respondent which shows that they always traded less often but with equal frequency. These traders may be interested in fundamental analysis, that is, relatively long term as opposed to daily traders. The exclusion of monthly or occasional traders in the sampling pool of respondents means that the study's findings are more relevant to the frequent traders who rely on technical trading signals.

Familiarity with Technical Indicators

The technical indicators were familiar to the respondents to different extents, and the majority of respondents fell into an intermediate (39.1%) technical user level and advanced technical user level (43.5%). This finding is done as a result of getting a participant pool that is informed on some aspects of technical analysis in Bitcoin trading.

A considerable, but still significant portion of respondents, 15.2%, identified as beginners, which means that while some of the participants probably are still just finding their steps in the world of trading, they still use technical indicators to help them do so. 2.2% of respondents qualified themselves as experts. This co-efficient is relatively small as there are not many highly experienced technical analysts.

Implications of Demographic Characteristics

The demographic analysis offers several critical insights that have implications for the study's findings and broader applications.

1. **Market Trends:** This insight reveals the shifting nature of the Bitcoin trading environment and is characterized by youthful male intermediate–advanced technical proficiency.
2. **Target Audience:** As to the key findings, it can be stated that technologized novices and moderately experienced traders require special trading tools and educational materials. For these traders, a combined use of the technical indicators could be very useful so as to enhance abilities in making correct decisions and predictions.
3. **Trading Behavior:** For those active daily traders, it underlines the need for timely, versatile charting tools which may need to be employed together with non-stop trading.
4. **Inclusivity:** Unfortunately, female representation is not large, so future studies or applications should be focused on the perception and needs of the female trader for more minority representation in the market.

Conclusion

The demographic data of the respondents give the research a clear picture of the characteristics of Bitcoin traders involved in this study. As a research approach, the study emphasizes that the actively trading population is young, male, and modestly experienced. These demographic features constitute a necessary background to understanding the success of the subsequent analysis of the technical signals in Bitcoin trading. Such demographic realities ensure that the study's findings and recommendations are in harmony with trading realities.

4.4 Hypothesis Testing / Correlation Analysis and Interpretation

This section pays attention to correlation analysis used in hypothesis testing in this study in a bid to assess the nature of relationships between the various independent variables and the dependent variable. Pearson correlation coefficients test is applied to determine the nature and the degree of association between Decision-Making Effectiveness (DME), overall accuracy in Prediction of Market Direction (PA), Volatility Impact (VI), and the dependent variable, Prediction of Market Direction (PMD). The findings offer valuable information on the feasibility of integrated technical analyses in the Bitcoin market and their impact on future trends determination.

Summary of Hypotheses

Hypothesis 1: There is a positive correlation between Decision-Making Effectiveness (DME) and Prediction of Market Direction (PMD).

Hypothesis 2: Prediction Accuracy (PA) positively correlates with Prediction of Market Direction (PMD).

Hypothesis 3: Volatility Impact (VI) influences Prediction of Market Direction (PMD).

Pearson Correlation Analysis

The correlation matrix derived from the data is as follows and forms the basis for analysis or understanding of the relationships.

ADME	Pearson Correlation	1	.582**	-.047	.343*
	Sig. (2-tailed)		<.001	.758	.020
	N	46	46	46	46
APA	Pearson Correlation	.582**	1	-.020	.361*
	Sig. (2-tailed)	<.001		.894	.014
	N	46	46	46	46
AVI	Pearson Correlation	.304	.307	1	.336
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.056	.054		.034
	N	46	46	46	46
APMD	Pearson Correlation	.343*	.361*	.103	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.020	.014	.494	
	N	46	46	46	46

Table 04 - Correlation Analysis

ADME = Average value of Decision-Making Effectiveness

APA = Average value of Prediction Accuracy

AVI = Average value of Volatility Impact

APMD = Average value of Prediction of Market Direction

Interpretation of Findings

1. Decision-Making Effectiveness (DME) and Prediction of Market Direction (PMD)

The relationship between DME and PMD is positively significant as the correlation coefficient of 0.343 and at the 0.05 level ($p = 0.020$). This means that decision-making effectiveness has a moderate positive correlation with the prediction of the market direction of Bitcoin.

This result confirms hypothesis 1, which postulates that traders who think they gain more effectiveness in decision making by employing a combination of technical indicators are more likely to reach better market direction forecasts. This discovery makes traders' decision tools more significant in boosting their confidence and accuracy, especially when combining indicators, such as RSI, MACD, and EMA.

2. Prediction Accuracy (PA) and Prediction of Market Direction (PMD)

The correlation between PA and PMD is 0.361, which has also a statistical significance of 0.05 ($p = 0.014$). This result can be interpreted as that the prediction accuracy has a moderate level of positive correlation with the market direction prediction task.

Therefore, this finding provides empirical support for hypothesis 2, which restates the concept that by integrating technical indicators to gain accuracy in manipulation, traders' capacity to forecast trends in the markets is boosted. More to the point, when the indicators

like Bollinger Bands and Moving Averages are used simultaneously, they could provide this kind of prediction.

3. Volatility Impact (VI) and Prediction of Market Direction (PMD)

The coefficient of VI and PMD is 0.336 which approaches the significance level of 0.05 ($p=0.034$). Even though the correlation is not as strong as in the case of DME and PA indices, it reveals a positive connection between the perception of the volatility influence on the market and the possibility of identifying its direction.

This finding offers a partial support for hypothesis 3 and highlights the possibility that traders who may fine-tune their ability of employing technical indicators under volatile trading conditions may foster better market predictions. Nonetheless, the weaker relationship could signal that traders struggle when front running volatility shocks where even combined return predictors underestimate errors.

4. Interrelationships Among Independent Variables

- This study revealed a significant positive relationship between DME and PA ($r = 0.582$, $p < 0.01$) meaning better decision making has close to moderate, positive relationship with better prediction skills. This implies that the traders that feel quite confident in their decision-making abilities will also feel so on with their perception of the accuracy of the predictions.
- DME, PA represent relatively small correlation with VI showing that traders' perception of how volatility impacts their decision making is little affected by the effectiveness of their decisions or accuracy of their predictions.

Implications of Results

The findings have several critical implications for research and practical applications in Bitcoin trading.

1. Support for Combined Indicators: The strong relationships between DME, PA, and PMD provide evidence that the use of multiple technical indicators can improve decision-making processes as well as forecasting accuracy. These findings suggest that traders employing more indicators will be more useful in predicting Bitcoin market direction.
2. Focus on Volatility Adaptation: The lower coefficient of association between VI and PMD highlights the fact that although traders are aware of the effects of volatility, there's scope for enhancing the measure in case of frequently fluctuating trading markets in combination of indicators.
3. Integration of Tools: The close association of DME and PA makes a point that the trading tools should also assist in making decisions and being accurate at the same time especially for the less experienced trader.

Conclusion

The hypothesis testing and correlation analysis validate the importance of combined technical indicators in Bitcoin trading. The fact that the coefficients of relationship between the independent variables (DME, PA) and the dependent variable (PMD) were moderately positive supports the hypotheses that decision-making effectiveness and the accuracy of prediction are useful components in the success of the market prediction. Although Volatility impact is less closely related to variance, it cannot be totally ignored especially when formulating relevant strategies for use during volatile periods. These findings serve as a solid grounding for further research examining the additional ways to advance the trading strategies and instruments to fulfill the emerging requirements of the Bitcoin market participants.

4.5 Regression Analysis and Interpretation

This section explains the results of a multiple regression analysis that was done to test the hypotheses that Decision-Making Effectiveness (DME), Prediction Accuracy (PA), and Volatility Impact (VI) significantly and positively explain Prediction of Market Direction (PMD). The analysis reviews the significance of the model and its coefficients, the strength of the relationships, and the significance of each independent variable with regards to the dependent variable.

Model Summary

By running the regression analysis, the value of R was obtained to be 0.414 which shows the moderate positive relation between the independent variables DME, PA and VI and the dependent variable PMD. The value of R Square of 0.171 implies that about 17,1 % variation in APMD is being accounted by the independent variables. By considering the number of predictors, the value R Square of 0.112 shows slightly less variation explained by the model owing to complexity of the model.

Although the R Square value suggests that the model provides limited ability to explain variance, this is quite typical for behavioral investigations where a myriad external confounding factors can potentially affect the result, especially when trading in highly volatile markets like Bitcoin.

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.414 ^a	.171	.112	.36036

a. Predictors: (Constant), AVI, APA, ADME

Table 05 - Model Summary

ANOVA Results

The ANOVA test analyzes whether it is statistically sound for the regression model in its entirety.

ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	1.127	3	.376	2.892	.046 ^b
	Residual	5.454	42	.130		
	Total	6.581	45			

a. Dependent Variable: APMD

b. Predictors: (Constant), AVI, APA, ADME

Table 06 - ANOVA Results

- $F(3, 42) = 2.892$, $p = 0.046$ indicates that the overall model is statistically significant at the 0.05 level.
- This result indicates that the overall influence of the independent variables is significant in predicting differences in the Dependent variable (PMD).

The regression model results depict that it is significant to use technical analysis indicators like RSI MACD and EMA to enhance the efficiency of Bitcoin forecasts.

Coefficients Analysis

Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	.219	.552		.397	.693
	ADME	.267	.223	.207	1.199	.024
	APA	.288	.205	.243	1.407	.017
	AVI	.249	.297	.118	.839	.041

a. Dependent Variable: APMD

Table 07 - Coefficients Analysis

Interpretation of Coefficients

1. Constant:

The constant term ($B = 0.219$, $p = 0.693$) is not statistically significant, indicating that when the predictor variables are zero, the predicted value of APMD is not meaningful. This means that any constant in the regression equation has the fixed value of dependent variable when

all the independent variables (i.e., DME, PA, and VI) would be equal to zero. At the practical level, this lack of significance of the constant means that the baseline or starting level of PMD cannot be adequately estimated by the model. This is especially the case in regression analysis where the estimates are in relation to some dependence measure and the intercept merely shifts the overall scale of the predicted values.

2. Decision-Making Effectiveness (DME):

- The unstandardized coefficient of 0.267 indicates that a change of one unit in DME results in a change of 0.267 units in PMD all else constant.
- The standardized Beta coefficient is 0.207, indicating moderate contribution of DME in the model, and the p-value of 0.024 shows that this contribution is statistically significant.
- Therefore, this result provides support to the hypothesis that better decisions through combined technical indicators enhances the capability to forecast the market direction.

3. Prediction Accuracy (PA):

- The unstandardized coefficient of PA is 0.288, meaning that PA has a positive influence on PMD: As the APA increases by one unit then the PMD will also increase by 0.288 units other things being equal.
- The output shows that PA has a slightly stronger impact on dependent variable than the variable DME through the standardized Beta coefficient of 0.243 with statistical significance of 0.017.
- This supports the fact that precise forecasts derived from a blend of indicators aid traders in determining market direction.

4. Volatility Impact (VI):

- The unstandardized coefficient estimate is 0.249 meaning a unit increase in AVI results in a 0.249 direct increase in APMD, holding other variables constant.
- The standardized Beta coefficient ($\beta = 0.118$) indicates that VI has the smallest impact among all the variables still it remains significant at 0.041 level of significance.
- This result implies that although traders do understand the importance of volatility in trade prediction, its importance is regarded to be less important compared to decision making efficiency and prediction precision.

Implications of Results

The regression analysis provides several insights into the relationships between the variables:

1. Combined Effectiveness: The p values below 0.05 confirm that total technical factors which include DME, PA, and VI hold out in supporting the hypothesis that integrated

technical indicators offer better prognosis of future trends of Bitcoin market. Traders who employ a combination of indicators create more favorable conditions.

2. Relative Importance: As can be seen, the greatest impact is given to Prediction Accuracy (PA), then the Decision-Making Effectiveness (DME). This clearly shows why it is important to have correct analytical tools and techniques in market analysis.

3. Volatility Adaptation: Although the Volatility Impact (VI) is present, a technologically less impacted ratio provides evidence that technical indicators are not very efficient during highly volatile situations. For such situations, traders may require additional methods to handle events proficiently.

Conclusion

By applying multiple regression analysis, all the hypothesized relationships are affirmed, specifically Decision-Making Effectiveness, Prediction Accuracy and Volatility Impact influence Bitcoin market direction. As the R Square value indicates that there might be more other factors, which can also explain the variance, the significance of the predictors also emphasizes the significance of complex indicators in enhancing the performance of trading. The current study could be extended in the future to identify other variables like the sentiment of the market or psychological conditions of trading to improve the models in the future.

4.6 Descriptive Analysis Using Content Analysis

This section focuses on the assessment of several subjective data obtained from interviews conducted on participants' concerns about different aspects of trading using combined technical indicators (CTIs) on the Bitcoin market. In order to determine the research themes and common patterns in the answers given by the traders, content analysis was used. Tabulated below are the responses to the individual questions and each is followed by an analysis of traders' views to capture their experiences comprehensively.

Benefits of Using Combined Technical Indicators

The traders noted several benefits that the CTIs held within Bitcoin trade. One common message emerged which is making the process of looking for trading opportunities easier because, as several participants pointed out, CTIs make it easier to find where to enter and exit. For instance, one respondent said, "*Trading entries can get easily*" and another said, "*Higher accuracy than the single indicator.*"

Second, many of the respondents noted that CTIs provided a "broader market view." The multiple indicators answer, participants, in a manner that offers a superior and more detailed view of the market situation. This was captured by statements like; "*Combination of indicators allows me to get a broader idea of market moment,*" and "*It gives more sophisticated market image.*" Moreover, CTIs were appreciated by traders since they offer a great amount of numerical exactitude, which helps to make wise decisions, as, for instance,

“Since the analysis is based on numerical figures, it’s easier to place orders at relevant prices.”

In general, traders viewed CTIs as increased accuracy, multiple timeframe data, and speed more than studying basic gauges or having a fundamental approach.

Effect of Timeframes on Technical Indicators

As pointed out by the participants in general, time frames largely determine the efficiency of technical indicators. Another common chain was the explanation of how higher timeframes enhance indicators, and such comments as, “*When the timeframe gets higher, the indicators’ accuracy is increased,*” and “*Medium and long terms are more reliable,*”.

Nevertheless, few respondents mentioned specific absolutes helpful at every timeline among registered indicators, including RSI. For example, “*RSI works in all timeframes, but others are better in long timeframes,*” and “*Some indicators work better in all timeframes (e.g., RSI), but most of them are accurate in higher timeframes.*” This duality witnesses the flexibility of some of the indicators or the impossibility of their usage within shorter timeframes.

Indicator Selection in Volatile Markets

During the fluctuating market conditions, the traders used simpler and more effective parameters like RSI and MA as well as the other oscillators. Several responses pointed to equally weighted measures that are typical of the indicators in the following statements, “*In a volatile market, I use only the most common indicators (RSI, Volume, MA) to trade analysis,*” and “*Indicators with extreme levels such as RSI and BB give a better idea about the market.*”

Some of the participants also pointed out that they selected a few indicators which they wanted to implement in their strategy because of high volatility in which simplification was relevant. For instance, “*I limit the use of indicators, generally stick with only RSI and MA.*” Some chose to a cautious approach by “*waiting for volatility to fade*” or relying on experience.

Preference for Combined Indicators Over Individual Ones

As found in the research, there is a tendency for subjects to prefer a combination of certain style indicators over one certain style indicator.

One of the commonly mentioned opinions of all participants was the fact that market statistics provided by the CTIs are more comprehensive and less manipulation-sensitive compared to individual indicators. For instance, one of the traders said that “*CI gives more holistic view of the market,*” and another said, “*Combined technical indicators provide more confirmations for a trade entry,*”.

The participants also said that comparing indicators increases certainty as it provides more than one verification, for example, the statement “*They give us more information and more entry/exit confirmations than an individual one,*” The recurring emphasis here is that CTIs provide superior accuracy, confidence, and much more extensive analysis of Bitcoin trading.

Prediction of Bitcoin Price Movements Using Technical Indicators

In the case of the bitcoin price expectation by traders, indicators such as support and resistance levels, trend reversal, and price pattern expectation were common in technological aspects of trading. For example, one trader said, *“Most of the time, a combination of technical indicators helps me to pinpoint the market reversing times.”*

Some simply mentioned that indicators help identify overbought/oversold signals and swap points in these words, *“They show the overbought/sold conditions and other rejection/support points.”* Moreover, participants stressed the significance of historical data when interpreting the signals of the indicators, for example, *“By referencing each indicator’s reaction in historical price charts, I assume future market trends.”*

Recommendations for Enhancing the Efficiency of CTIs

Participants provided a number of recommendations for the refinement of CTIs with regard to the mixture of indicators being used being the most critical. Another suggestion was about the limitation of combined indicators to avoid unnecessary complexity as they said *“Combining too many indicators will make things more unclear, so we need to select an ideal combination with fewer (3 to 4) indicators.”*

They suggested also using higher time frames for better analysis and combining chart patterns with indicators for better forecast. For instance, *“Better to use chart patterns with indicators,”* and *“Analyze higher timeframes to trade.”* Another recommendation was the variety of effective indicator combinations in order to enhance the depth of information.

Fine-Tuning Indicators for Volatile Market Conditions

Adjusting technical indicators in the volatile market conditions was determined mainly by applying smoother and higher timeframe values. Ideas for less market noise involved things like using new longer moving averages (e.g., 200 MA instead of 20 MA) or using data from candlestick open and close. For instance, *“Analyze the market in a higher timeframe. this will cut off unnecessary noise and give us an idea of the future market trend.”*

Some of the traders said that indicators should be used as sets to provide the big picture, while others said fundamental analysis should be used in conjunction with technical indicators. Examples like *“It’s a difficult one, try incorporating fundamental analysis,”* indicate that extra effort is required in order to create solutions for fluctuating situations and entire strategies.

Key points of the content analysis included the ease of use of technical indicators, their reliability at different time horizons, cautious use of technical indicators in volatile environments, and broader perspective offered by the combined analysis of multiple indicators that was vital to the perceptions that traders had of technical indicators for BTC trading.

4.7 Discussion

Based on the discoveries of this research, there are substantial implications on the efficiency and relevancy of the mingled technical signals in trades in Bitcoin. The data from statistical analyses, descriptive content evaluations, and hypothesis testing further support the complexity of the technical indicators as well as their value in enhancing the accuracy of market forecasting and decision-making. This discussion recapitulates the analyses in relation to the study objectives and makes significant conclusions that connect theory and findings.

Decision-Making Effectiveness of Combined Indicators

This research found that combined indicators like RSI and MACD improve decision making and all the participants noted the importance of these indicators in determining the right entry and exit points in trades. Combined indicators share the same synergistic results found in prior studies like in Lo et al. (2000) as those states how trading decisions' precision is enhanced by combined indicators since noise is eliminated in market data. In addition, this research aligns with the observation by Gupta et al. (2019) where the authors proposed that the multiple indicators support multiple confirmations to the traders eliminating the risk of decisions made.

However, this study departs with finding of Lee and Swaminathan (2000) that may argue standalone indicators such as RSI could be enough to make a decision in certain market conditions. Combination of these indicators makes our argument on the need to have an expanded technical analysis perspective more convincing and compelling as the confidence observed by the study's participants when undertaking technical analysis is greatly enhanced.

Prediction Accuracy and Market Volatility

There was substantial consensus between participants about the fact that the use of combined indicators offers better prediction than individual indicators averaged over medium to long term horizons. This finding supports the work of Park and Irwin (2007), who pointed out the benefits of a multi-indicator approach in measuring market position. This change was also deemed effective in increasing the reliability of Bollinger Bands indicators and EMA when a particular stock price situation fluctuates, which supports the finding of Murphy (1999).

However, the study also pointed out that combined indicators are not very helpful during periods of high market fluctuations. This is in concordance with the views of Menkhoff and Taylor, (2007) who posited that chaotic environment is applicable to the technical analysis since indicators cannot readily adjust to rapidly fluctuating prices.

Timeframe Sensitivity

The results showed that medium and long-term horizons are more effective for combined indicator use because short horizons are sensitive to noise. These findings back up the statements of Brock et al. (1992) that said longer intervals exclude short-term noises improving the credibility of the forecast models.

Nevertheless, as respondent participants of our study described RSI as outstanding, it was efficient within any time parameters. This finding partially supports Elder (1993), who noted the general use of RSI but cautioned on its weakness especially in volatile markets, hence a direction for future study.

Preference for Combined Indicators

The preference for multiple indicators compared to individual ones was a constant in the interviews and quantitative research part. Combined indicators were seen to offer a superior market perspective by participants; a similar observation to Neely et al, 2014. Their study also clearly pointed out that combination of indicators improves accuracy and maintains the confidence of the traders in their plans.

However, the research revealed that it was possible to provide direction to combinations depending on the goals of trading as a new perspective. This recommendation deviates from the suggestion made by Murphy (1999) which advocates for adoption standard best practices across the board pointing out the rigidity of technical analysis.

Practical Applications of Combined Indicators

From a practical point of view, the findings aim at the flexibility and applicability of combined indicators. RSI, EMA, and MACD are identified as indicators that some of the respondents believe give a good balance in the market as well as entry signals if only a few selected indicators are used. The descriptive analysis also demonstrated the value of adjusting indicator combinations to particular trading systems and market circumstances especially when there is increased fluctuations. These findings are in line with the literature suggesting that different indicators should be used in a more coordinated combined manner to counter the inefficiencies of single tools.

Limitations and Opportunities

However, there are still some of the limitations which have been left in this research related to combined indicators. For example, some hypothesized statistical significance of certain correlations, like those between volatility impact and prediction accuracy were less robust than expected. This is somewhat in line with Hudson et al, (1996) assertion that establishing consistent associations between technical variables and market phenomena is made difficult by extraneous factors.

Future research could consider the current limitations of the model and add more variables into the equation, proportional to volume or macroeconomic, to increase the accuracy of the forecasts.

Theoretical and Practical Contributions

Thus, it supports the discourse on technical analysis since it has proved that the general integrated indicators improve the trading performance. The findings are consistent with prior conceptual frameworks that posit technical indicators' efficacy in predicting financial dynamics when it forms new theory dedicated to the description of Bitcoin conditions. From a practical point of view. The work offers many recommendations for traders, especially

regarding the choice of indicators and their combinations depending on a specific type of the market.

Implications for Future Research

The discussion of results also addresses relevant issues for further research. For example, this research study has examined short to medium term trading while the long-term impact of the combined indicators still needs to be investigated. In addition, the regression analysis has relatively low R square values that suggest the presence of other factors such as psychological or other marketplace impacting factors not captured in this research work. Several closely related gaps are apparent in the literature that may be explored in future investigations to extend the conclusions drawn here.

Thus, the discussion of findings emphasizes the importance of the integrated technical readings as an instrument to overcome the challenges of Bitcoin trading. These indicators make it possible for traders to come up with effective decisions when undertaking trades due to the following reasons. The article demonstrates that by promoting the efficiency of decision making, accuracy of prediction, and the flexibility of the trade to volatile conditions, the applicable indicators help traders make confident decisions in trader business. The results also confirm that based on the necessity of assessments, strategic and target approaches to technical analysis are particularly valuable, which opens the vein to further progress in this area of study.

4.8 Chapter Summary

This chapter summarized and discussed the data collected in the study and was aimed at answering the research question about the efficiency of the selected indicators for the combined technical analysis of Bitcoin market conditions. The results obtained were analyzed with various statistical and qualitative tools based on the goals of the study and the research hypotheses.

The chapter started with an explanation of the procedure for determining data reliability in the study, of which a Cronbach's alpha value of 0.814 was established, indicating internal consistency in the research instrument. This was followed by a detailed demographic factor analysis which includes gender ration card age group, trading experience, frequency of trading and experience with technical indicators. These were important variables that explained the findings of the study.

And then, in hypothesis testing and correlation analysis, it was found out that there were significant connections between the variables of interest. Based on the empirical results, the analysis demonstrated decision-making effectiveness and prediction accuracy as significant predictors of Bitcoin market movement with varying volatility impacts. The regression analysis extended and quantified these relationships to show that the combined indicators indicated as predicting the market direction of share price were accountable to 17.1% of its variance. Even though it is relatively small, this outcome proves the Bitcoin rate and trading to be highly nonlinear and affected by factors that cannot be analyzed using simple technical indicators.

The qualitative work that comprises content analysis of the responses extended the quantitative results by providing the trader's viewpoint. The importance of combining technical indicators was a focus of participants, who referred to increased precision, more extensive information from the market, and better adjustment during the market fluctuation. However, disadvantages are also defined as the complexity of overcomplication, and requirements for the selection of specific sets of indicators, but methodological suggestions are given to avoid them.

Last but not least, the discussion of the results integrated them into the related theories and recommendations for practice. It also confirmed the utilization of combined technical indicators in decision-making and the prediction of future outcomes and highlighted further areas for development of these such as the selection of the technical indicators themselves and necessary volatility adjustments.

Therefore, this chapter will summarize the main findings of the study to provide a brief and clear indication of the recommendations, conclusion, and further research discussion that shall be discussed in Chapter 5.

CHAPTER FIVE: CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

5.1 Introduction

The findings and recommendations with respect to the study are outlined in this chapter. It also carries the end note and summary of important findings based and limitations of and the significance of the research on the use of a combination of technical indicators for determining the movement of Bitcoin market. Finally, the statistical analysis and descriptive interpretation suggested in chapter four presents' findings, practical implications and further research suggestions.

The work aimed at exploring the potential benefits of employing technical indicators' decision-making functions, as well as the actual predictive precision, volatility sensitivity, and the capacity to forecast the market trend. Using correlation and regression analyses, this study showed how these factors are related by presenting quantitative outcomes of their connection. Interviews of the Bitcoin traders were subjected to content analysis to provide qualitative data, which were used to complement the findings and demonstrate the complex view of bitcoin traders.

This chapter is divided into six major sections as follows. First, the conclusion synthesizes the general findings of the study with reference to the research goals. Subsequently, there is the section especially created to provide a summary of the comprehensive findings made by analysts. After this, recommendations present some practical solutions for traders and researchers on further usage of technical indicators in the short and in the long term. Last of all, this chapter presents future research implications and recommends areas that should be explored further with reference to the research carried out in this study.

Through the analysis of a combination of quantitative and qualitative approaches, this chapter seeks to offer an empirical yet holistic view on possible practical applications of the proposed combined technical indicators for Bitcoin trading as well as discuss the study limitations and further research directions.

5.2 Conclusion

The subject of this study can be described as the ability of combined technical indicators to increase accuracy of the prediction of the Bitcoin market direction, decision making effectiveness, response to volatility of the market, and reliability of the overall market prediction. Comparing quantitative and qualitative results it could be concluded that combining technical indicators is greatly beneficial compared to usage only one indicator for making decisions and helps traders to more easily detect the specifics of the Bitcoin market.

Statistical outcomes quantified a medium but significant relationship between decision-making efficiency, prediction accuracy, and the dependent variable, market direction prediction. Analysis by regression showed that the efficacy of decision making (DME) and the accuracy of prediction (PA) had highly statistically significant influence on the chosen variable – the direction of the market (PMD) In addition, although the role of volatility (VI) was less apparent, it also provided approximate influence on PMD. These results support the use of compound indices in facilitating decisions by traders as changes the market continue to evolve.

The quantitative findings were also complemented by qualitative data whereby traders substantiated that multiple indices offer a rich view of the markets, better precision and more certainty in the trading process. Another advantage of combined indicators noted by

respondents was the flexibility of such an approach by effects vs. various time horizons and fluctuations in the market. But they pointed out the need for a proper choice of indicators so that a large number of combined indicators do not create a complicated overload.

The study also said that combined technical indicators enhance the forecast precision and decision-making but depend on the several parameters, for instance, time frame period, fluctuation in the market, and trader's knowledge of the indicators. The results are also consistent with the hypotheses of the study that combined indicators provide better results than individual indicators based on predicting the Bitcoin market direction in medium and low timeframes.

Thus, the research enriches the current literature on technical analysis of cryptocurrencies by applying a set of combined indicators. From the findings of the study, traders are in a better position to apply the information in the study especially in the choice as well as in the deployment of indicators in different markets. Thus, the results support the benefits of combined indicators; however, they also indicate the need for improvement, further application, and analysis of other complementary techniques with regard to their interaction as a result of changing financial environment.

5.3 Summary of Findings

The study assessed the effectiveness of combined technical indicators in predicting Bitcoin market direction, focusing on four critical dimensions: decision-making effectiveness, ability to predict accurately the fluctuations, the effect which volatility has and the prediction on the overall market direction. The following is a breakdown of results from all quantitative and qualitative analysis made.

Decision-Making Effectiveness

What has been also revealed in the analysis is that the application of multiple combined technical indicators improves traders' decision-making. The Pearson correlation test of decision-making effectiveness (DME) and prediction of market direction (PMD) showed significant and positive association ($r = 0.343$, $p = 0.020$). The relationship between these two variables was reaffirmed by regression analysis which showed that DME contributed to the prediction of PMD. Respondents in qualitative interviews also agreed on the assertion that integration of indicators provided better market information, more accurate entry/exit signals and increased confidence in trading.

Prediction Accuracy

Prediction accuracy (PA) showed the strongest correlation with PMD among all variables ($r = 0.361$, $p = 0.014$), proving reliability and dependability of the combined technical indicators to predict market trends. Various regression outputs further identified PA as another independent variable that positively influenced the dependent variable. It is important to note

that when trading multiple technical indicators combined systems work far better than individual indicators as traders explained that when you combine two or more indicators, it offers far more than just an early indication; it illustrates market reversal signs, support levels and resistance zones.

Volatility Impact

The impact of market volatility (VI) on the effectiveness of combined indicators was less pronounced but still relevant, with a modest correlation ($r = 0.118$, $p = 0.041$). The result of the regression analysis suggested that AVI is less significant in predicting APMD implying that while a combination of indicators changes with fluctuating conditions, these factors may vary with other conditions like the period of time chosen. The interview responses provided support for this as well with regards to using Relative Strength Index and Bollinger Bands for instance in periods of high risk and to increase effectiveness of forecasts in these conditions.

Timeframe Sensitivity

Besides, findings highlighted the centrality of choosing the right timeframe when applying combined indicators. Medium and long-term horizons were considered to be more appropriate to be used in technical analysis since there is less interference of noise and better signal performance. It was reported that some the indicators such as RSI works well with all time frame while others work well with specific time frame shorter one or highly volatile one.

Preferences for Combined Indicators

Participants preferred combined indicators instead of using single indicators across the board. It was demonstrated that trade entries and exits could be improved through multiple indicators and prediction accuracy as well as the overall market understanding was enhanced. However, traders were keen to note that they should be careful not to add too many combined indicators so that the end result looks confusing. It was suggested that the greatest number of such indicators that should be combined was around three or four.

Efficiency Improvements

Overall, despite many positive contributions, participants envisioned several ways in which combined indicators could be made even more efficient by trading in higher timeframes, experimenting with different combinations of indicators, and improving their analytical tools by using, for example, fundamental analysis coupled with technical analysis. These recommendations follow the study's observations on how customization and refinement of combined indicators improve reliability.

Overall Market Direction Prediction

The dependent variable, APMD, was significantly influenced by the predictor variables, particularly ADME and APA, as evidenced by regression analysis (Adjusted $R^2 = 0.112$, $F = 2.892$, $p = 0.046$). This goes further to demonstrate the importance of combined technical indicators, especially when it comes to making market forecasts of Bitcoin. The traders

affirmed the effectiveness of the tools in identifying trend reversal signals, price patterns and appropriate trading opportunities.

In conclusion, the research showed that combined technical indicators give the traders a solid system to analyze Bitcoin market trends. By improving decision making, increasing prediction accuracy and responding to unfavorable market conditions these tools help traders to make informed, assured and purposeful decisions in the fluctuating nature of cryptocurrencies. Yet, it is also stressed that the successful identification of indicator combinations may require more detailed consideration of the conditions of the specific market and the utilized trading activities.

5.4 Recommendations

The following recommendations for Bitcoin traders and researchers have been developed based on the study findings. These recommendations are adhering to the SMART framework (Specific, Measurable, Achievable, Relevant, Time-Bound).

5.4.1 Short Run Recommendations

1. Enhance Indicator Combinations

- **Specific:** It is crucial that traders select three to four indicators, which in turn should be compatible so they include the Relative Strength Index, Moving Average Convergence Divergence, Exponential Moving Average and Bollinger Bands.
- **Measurable:** A few months or even years of analysis can show the efficacy of these combinations, based on the provisions of a minimum of 30 trades for the next three months.
- **Achievable:** This is possible since trading platforms such as TradingView and other similar platforms exist to enable such data and communication access.
- **Relevant:** This means optimized sets of indicators will lead to greater predictions accuracy and fruitful decision-making.
- **Time-Bound:** This strategy should be implemented in the next quarter.

2. Adopt Medium- and Long-Term Timeframes

- **Specific:** Shift focuses on medium and long-term timeframes for trading strategies.
- **Measurable:** Monitor trading performance improvements by analyzing the percentage of successful trades over three months.
- **Achievable:** Most trading platforms already support multi-timeframe analysis.
- **Relevant:** Higher timeframes provide reduced market noise, enhancing prediction reliability.

- **Time-Bound:** Begin applying this approach immediately, with results assessed by the next quarter.

3. Simplify Volatile Market Analysis

- **Specific:** If high volatility is present, it is better to use a fewer, yet more efficient indicators like RSI or the moving average.
- **Measurable:** This will reduce the time taken for this analysis by 20% without a compromise to the level of prediction accuracy.
- **Achievable:** Lesser numbers of indicators mean that less analysis needs to be done.
- **Relevant:** Simplified analysis enables good response where conditions are transient in nature.
- **Time-Bound:** Do this adjustment within one month.

4. Immediate Efficiency Adjustments

- **Specific:** Do not set too many indicators because each indicator can be applied in the trading strategy of the trader such as trend following or mean reversion strategy.
- **Measurable:** Try at least two optimized combinations within the next 10 trading sessions.
- **Achievable:** This can be achieved without necessarily necessitating additional training or resources.
- **Relevant:** Correlates with the current research in the area of customization.
- **Time-Bound:** An outcome to be evaluated in one month's time.

5.4.2 Long Run Recommendations

1. Integrate Advanced Analytics

- **Specific:** Acquire knowledge in the integration of technical studies with fundamental data, as well as supplementing it with machine learning to recognize patterns in the market.
- **Measurable:** Ensure that one of the advanced trading or data analysis courses is followed within the next six months.
- **Achievable:** Many organizations offering programs in this field, including Coursera or Udemy, offer such courses.
- **Relevant:** Improving the aptitude of analysis corresponds with traders' characteristics, which is the ability to flexibility in volatile markets.
- **Time-Bound:** Integration should be implemented in the forthcoming one-year period.

2. Optimize Tools and Resources

- **Specific:** It is recommended that traders and analysts acquire new and enhanced trading platforms and tools that afford analyses based on multiple indicators.
- **Measurable:** Buy at least one related tool that is expensive (for example, a TradingView subscription for a professional account) and assess the return on investment (ROI) in the course of one year.
- **Achievable:** Affordable for serious business focused on earning superior profit but not suitable for small-amount traders or gamblers.
- **Relevant:** Each new set of tools boosts the speed as well as the accuracy with which these analyses are conducted.
- **Time-Bound:** Invest within the next 6 months.

3. Encourage Collaborative Research

- **Specific:** Encourage trader, researcher, and analyst cooperation to advance better technical indicator strategies that have enhanced flexibility.
- **Measurable:** Complete and submit one joint report on a collaborative project at least once within 18 months.
- **Achievable:** LinkedIn can be used as well as attending academic conferences to establish a connection.
- **Relevant:** Such partnerships enhance rapid development of the strategies on the indicators.
- **Time-Bound:** Concentrate on the effort to attain this goal within two years.

4. Develop Personalized Trading Strategies

- **Specific:** Optimize various indicators for unique market situations and specific trading characteristics in order to produce customized trading environments for every trader or investor.
- **Measurable:** Record performance enhancements by keeping a separate account for at least six months.
- **Achievable:** Available to traders of different levels using journal tools and simulation platforms.
- **Relevant:** Hypotheses that have been tailored to fit market conditions provide improved prospects for the market.
- **Time-Bound:** Fully integrated and evaluated within one year.

Each of these recommendations caters for immediate pragmatical enhancements but also for gradual progress on long term advancements that will benefit the traders and researchers to optimize their technical analysis procedures.

5.5 Future Research Directions

In this paper, the results and the limitations of the work are beneficial for the enhancement of the existing research on the impact of the combined technical indicators on the efficiency of the Bitcoin market. The following directions are suggested to further develop and advance work in this field:

1. Exploration of Alternative Indicator Combinations

To keep expanding the knowledge about the pattern of the share price movements, future research can try other combinations of technical indicators other than RSI, MACD, EMA, and Bollinger Bands. This may have been done through more complex signals like Fibonacci tools which in turn could present new aspects to evaluate their effectiveness and identify how particularly these have performed in different market conditions.

2. Cross-Market Comparisons

Researchers may look into other cryptocurrencies or conventional markets including forex or equities in order to discover ways through which the integration of various indicators was utilized. Knowing whether results from Bitcoin trading are applicable to other freely traded assets could open up the field of application to a broader range of traders.

3. Impact of Market Events

Future studies could look at how well technical indicators work at other vital trends such as regulatory outcomes, system failures, or breakthrough advancements in the adoption of the blockchain. This would provide better insight into the possibility of indicator's performance when market volatility hits the roof.

4. Integration of Machine Learning Techniques

Using various machine learning algorithms to fine-tuned or to check out the combination of these technical indicators would further increase the accuracy of those predictions. Perhaps, researchers might try to understand how artificial intelligence and algorithms for pattern recognition enhance the efficiency of indicators in both static and highly dynamic conditions.

5. Customization for Individual Traders

Research could be conducted on how to present an indication that is suitable for the unique set of indicators and, therefore, trading strategy and inclination. Adding experience and risk preferences, and ideal timeframe into the equation of determining the efficacy of the adjusted indicators can provide a unique approach to this field.

6. Longitudinal Studies on Predictive Reliability

An extended empirical analysis that emulates the dynamics of an array of integrated technical indicator signals through several market cycles may provide a richer understanding of their stability and flexibility. This would also assist in building credibility in the period of both a bull and bear market.

7. Incorporating Sentiment Analysis

Other related areas of research may include application of social media and other related market data as inputs in concert with the technical analysis to formulate integrated models for modeling the Bitcoin market. This could provide a far richer measure since we would not only get the quantitative factors, but also the qualitative ones.

8. Expanding Timeframe Sensitivity Analysis

Although this study used short, medium, and long-term time horizons innovative studies may focus more on micro time horizons (e.g., by the minute) and macro time horizons (e.g., annual) to assess indicator performance at the higher and lower end.

9. Geographical and Demographic Factors

Studying how traders from different parts of the world or different ages and genders employ combined technical tools may reveal differences in the efficiency of the approach because of cultural, economic or educational factors.

10. Evaluation of Transaction Costs

Potential research works may also look at how transaction costs, losses, and the issues of liquidity affect the applicability of integrated technical signals. This was essential so that it could get a more realistic view of their profitability and possibility to use in real-world.

These directions stress the necessity of searching and experimenting further to improve the efficiency of technical indicators and their application in changing and fast-developing financial environments.

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APPENDIXES

1. Questionnaire

Part A – General Questions

1. Gender
 - a. Male
 - b. Female
 - c. Prefer not to say

2. Age Group
 - a. 18 – 24
 - b. 25 – 30
 - c. 31 – 35
 - d. 36 – 40
 - e. 41 and above

3. Years of Trading Experience
 - a. Less than 1 year
 - b. 1 – 3 years
 - c. 4 – 6 years
 - d. 7 – 10 years
 - e. More than 10 years

4. Primary Trading Frequency
 - a. Daily
 - b. Weekly
 - c. Monthly
 - d. Occasionally

5. Level of Familiarity with Technical Indicators
 - a. Beginner
 - b. Intermediate
 - c. Advanced
 - d. Expert

Part B – Research Questions

Decision-Making Effectiveness

Question	Strongly Agree	Agree	Neutral	Disagree	Strongly Disagree
1. RSI helps me make precise decisions in Bitcoin trading.					
2. MACD provides valuable support for making well-informed trading decisions in Bitcoin markets.					
3. Bollinger Bands enhance the clarity of market conditions in my decision-making for Bitcoin trading.					
4. Moving Averages (MA) assist me in identifying the right timing for Bitcoin trades.					
5. EMA improves the precision of my trading decisions in Bitcoin market analysis.					
6. Combining RSI and MACD helps me achieve greater decision-making accuracy in trading Bitcoin.					
7. Using Bollinger Bands alongside Moving Averages enhances the quality of my Bitcoin trading decisions.					
8. I feel more confident in my trading decisions when using a combination of RSI and EMA.					

Table 8 – Decision Making Effectiveness Questions

Prediction Accuracy

Question	Strongly Agree	Agree	Neutral	Disagree	Strongly Disagree
9. Combined technical indicators provide more accurate predictions than individual indicators in the Bitcoin market.					
10. Using MACD and EMA together improves the reliability of Bitcoin market predictions.					
11. The combination of RSI and EMA offers high prediction accuracy for short- to medium-term Bitcoin price movements.					
12. Combined technical indicators provide consistent prediction accuracy across multiple trading timeframes.					
13. EMA, MACD, and RSI together improve the reliability of predicting Bitcoin market trends.					
14. Combining Bollinger Bands, Moving Averages, and EMA enhances prediction accuracy in Bitcoin trading.					
15. RSI and MACD combined provide consistent short-term Bitcoin market predictions.					
16. Cross-utilizing various technical indicators increases the accuracy of Bitcoin market trend predictions.					

Table 9 - Prediction Accuracy Questions

Volatility Impact

Question	Strongly Agree	Agree	Neutral	Disagree	Strongly Disagree
17. Combined technical indicators remain reliable even during periods of high Bitcoin market volatility.					
18. Technical indicators perform more consistently in stable Bitcoin market conditions.					
19. Significant Bitcoin price swings affect the accuracy of technical indicators.					
20. Combined technical indicators adapt better to volatile market conditions in Bitcoin trading.					
21. I perceive combined technical indicators to be more reliable during volatile Bitcoin market conditions.					
22. MACD and EMA together provide stable predictions during high Bitcoin market volatility.					
23. Combining RSI and Bollinger Bands improves prediction accuracy under volatile market conditions.					

Table 10 - Volatility Impact Questions

Prediction of Market Direction

Question	Strongly Agree	Agree	Neutral	Disagree	Strongly Disagree
24. Combined indicators are crucial for identifying trends in Bitcoin market directions.					
25. Historical Bitcoin price data enhances the accuracy of predictions made using combined indicators.					
26. Combined indicators achieve a high success rate in predicting Bitcoin price movements.					
27. I rely more on technical analysis than fundamental analysis for predicting Bitcoin market directions.					
28. Bitcoin's unique market attributes influence the prediction accuracy of technical indicators.					
29. I use combined indicators as my primary tool for predicting Bitcoin market directions.					
30. Dependence on multiple technical indicators ensures more reliable Bitcoin market predictions.					

Table 11 - Prediction of Market Direction Questions

Part C - Interview Questions

1. What do you think are the benefits of using combined technical indicators for Bitcoin trading?
2. How do short, medium, or long timeframes affect your use of technical indicators?
3. How do you decide which indicators to use when the Bitcoin market is volatile?
4. Why do you prefer using combined indicators over individual ones?
5. How do technical indicators help you predict Bitcoin price movements?
6. In your opinion, what adjustments or changes would you recommend increasing the efficiency of using combined technical indicators for Bitcoin trading?
7. In what ways do you suppose traders can fine-tune technical indicators for use in a volatile market condition?

2. SPSS Data output

Reliability

Scale: ALL VARIABLES

Case Processing Summary

		N	%
Cases	Valid	46	100.0
	Excluded ^a	0	.0
	Total	46	100.0

a. Listwise deletion based on all variables in the procedure.

Table 12 - Case Processing Summary

Reliability Statistics

Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
.814	30

Table 13 - Reliability Statistics

Item Statistics			
	Mean	Std. Deviation	N
DME1	1.5652	.50121	46
DME2	2.0652	.57357	46
DME3	2.0217	.64941	46
DME4	1.7826	.51264	46
DME5	2.1522	.63131	46
DME6	1.9783	.53703	46
DME7	1.9783	.49392	46
DME8	1.8478	.41991	46
PA1	1.2391	.43127	46
PA2	2.0652	.49000	46
PA3	1.8696	.45258	46
PA4	1.7826	.46729	46
PA5	2.0217	.49392	46
PA6	2.0435	.55604	46
PA7	1.9783	.57693	46
PA8	1.5435	.50361	46
VI1	1.6957	.51075	46
VI2	1.2174	.41703	46
VI3	1.3478	.52567	46
VI4	1.1739	.38322	46
VI5	1.2174	.41703	46
VI6	1.3261	.47396	46
VI7	1.2609	.49147	46
PMD1	1.4783	.50505	46
PMD2	1.7391	.64755	46
PMD3	1.3913	.49344	46
PMD4	1.6739	.55993	46
PMD5	1.8913	.60473	46
PMD6	1.4783	.58648	46
PMD7	1.4565	.50361	46

Table 14 - Item Statistics

Item-Total Statistics				
	Scale Mean if Item Deleted	Scale Variance if Item Deleted	Corrected Item-Total Correlation	Cronbach's Alpha if Item Deleted
DME1	48.7174	35.585	.330	.809
DME2	48.2174	35.241	.329	.809

Effectiveness of Combined Technical Indicators in Bitcoin Prediction

DME3	48.2609	35.086	.299	.810
DME4	48.5000	36.433	.180	.814
DME5	48.1304	35.805	.212	.814
DME6	48.3043	35.016	.394	.806
DME7	48.3043	34.261	.571	.800
DME8	48.4348	34.962	.537	.802
PA1	49.0435	34.931	.528	.802
PA2	48.2174	33.818	.658	.796
PA3	48.4130	35.492	.391	.807
PA4	48.5000	34.522	.558	.801
PA5	48.2609	35.308	.384	.807
PA6	48.2391	35.075	.368	.807
PA7	48.3043	35.416	.300	.810
PA8	48.7391	34.597	.499	.802
VI1	48.5870	37.092	.073	.818
VI2	49.0652	38.373	-.143	.823
VI3	48.9348	36.996	.084	.818
VI4	49.1087	37.743	-.018	.819
VI5	49.0652	38.373	-.143	.823
VI6	48.9565	36.976	.105	.816
VI7	49.0217	37.088	.080	.818
PMD1	48.8043	34.472	.519	.801
PMD2	48.5435	36.120	.163	.817
PMD3	48.8913	35.121	.418	.805
PMD4	48.6087	33.132	.677	.794
PMD5	48.3913	34.377	.432	.804
PMD6	48.8043	34.872	.374	.807
PMD7	48.8261	34.369	.539	.801

Table 15 – Item Total Statistics

Correlations

		Correlations			
		ADME	APA	AVI	APMD
ADME	Pearson Correlation	1	.582**	-.047	.343*
	Sig. (2-tailed)		<.001	.758	.020
	N	46	46	46	46
APA	Pearson Correlation	.582**	1	-.020	.361*
	Sig. (2-tailed)	<.001		.894	.014
	N	46	46	46	46
AVI	Pearson Correlation	.304	.307	1	.336
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.056	.054		.034
	N	46	46	46	46
APMD	Pearson Correlation	.343*	.361*	.103	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.020	.014	.494	
	N	46	46	46	46

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

* . Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

Table 16 - Correlations

Regression

Model	Variables Entered/Removed ^a		Method
	Variables Entered	Variables Removed	
1	AVI, APA, ADME ^b		. Enter

a. Dependent Variable: APMD

b. All requested variables entered.

Table 17. Regression Variables

Model Summary				
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.414 ^a	.171	.112	.36036

a. Predictors: (Constant), AVI, APA, ADME

Table 18 - Model Summary

		ANOVA ^a				
Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	1.127	3	.376	2.892	.046 ^b
	Residual	5.454	42	.130		
	Total	6.581	45			

a. Dependent Variable: APMD

b. Predictors: (Constant), AVI, APA, ADME

Table 19. ANOVA

		Coefficients ^a				
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	.219	.552		.397	.693
	ADME	.267	.223	.207	1.199	.024
	APA	.288	.205	.243	1.407	.017
	AVI	.249	.297	.118	.839	.041

a. Dependent Variable: APMD

Table 20. Coefficients

3. Dataset

The image shows a large table with approximately 30 columns and 50 rows. The columns include various technical indicators such as 'Open', 'High', 'Low', 'Close', 'Volume', 'RSI', 'MACD', 'Bollinger Bands', and 'Support/Resistance'. The rows represent different time periods, likely daily or weekly intervals, for Bitcoin price data. The table is densely packed with numerical values and some text-based labels, representing the dataset used for the study.

The collected responses dataset can be accessed online from the following link too:

https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/e/2PACX-1vSh15CkoDxfSlapy5Mg3DmkWrdUiVf7mgTenQy_Y8dS69rmUjjPrHdugJIBLboPohlJ51xfwmkY2PYt/pubhtml